

COMMUNITY-ROOTED & YOUTH-LED REPORT

ALIEF DISASTER PREPAREDNESS PROTOCOL

Preparing for tomorrow, today.

CREDITS & FUNDERS

Funded by the Resilient Cities Network. Lead Author: Tommy Wan. Student Editors & Writers: Julian Nguyen, Harrison Tran, Lander Gonzalez, Zody Calderon-Huerta, Allie Hogan, Ericka Chanchavac-Rosales, Sawsan Busari, Cindy Ukwu, and Yousif Al Mashhadi.

HARRIS COUNTY PRECINCT 4
COMMISSIONER
LESLEY BRIONES

With support from Texas State Representative Gene Wu's Office & Consulate General of Mexico in Houston.

"Sometimes it takes a natural disaster to reveal a social disaster." - Jim Wallis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We know all too well the consequences of disasters. From Hurricane Harvey and the D to extreme heat and straight-line Derecho winds, communities across the Houston area have been affected severely through family loss, economic detriment, damaged homes, and anguish. This is especially true in the Alief area in the heart of Southwest Houston. Too many community voices are not solicited or fully integrated into official disaster planning. This protocol report aims to change this narrative.

The Alief Disaster Preparedness Protocol stands as a report that represents a community-driven initiative to emergency planning, developed through extensive grassroots engagement with one of Houston's most diverse neighborhoods. Over the course of 2024, AliefVotes, a non-profit focused on youth civic leadership, led multiple community roundtable workshops, and two hands-on green infrastructure pocket prairie projects that gathered input from residents representing a multitude of languages and cultural backgrounds across the Alief area. This report encapsulates community feedback, resources in disaster preparation, and initiatives proposed—all led by youth leaders in Alief ISD.

Figure 1. Disaster Preparedness Student-Led Roundtable on September 13, 2025 at the Alief Neighborhood Center.

With the compounding threats of climate change, warming oceans, aging infrastructure, and a historic lack of community engagement, the creation of this report responds to an urgent demand for detailed, grassroots feedback, solicited through genuine community interaction and an open process. **This report was thus generated through intensive internal and external partner collaboration to ensure as many voices as possible are represented.**

Our principal focus as a non-profit is community engagement. Founded in 2022 by Alief student leaders, [AliefVotes](https://www.aliefvotes.org/) (<https://www.aliefvotes.org/>) is a nonprofit that empowers youth engagement in Alief, a working-class, immigrant community in Southwest Houston. Alief faces low voter turnout, economic divestment, and a lack of opportunities for youth leadership now. Situated in City Council District F, we are the “forgotten district.” In response, we built AliefVotes in collaboration with Houston City Councilwoman Tiffany D. Thomas (Councilwoman Thomas has represented District F and the Alief area since 2019 and is currently serving her second term as of the publication date).

With the funding and support of the Resilient Cities Network, AliefVotes was empowered to take on the critical challenge of data collection, report writing, and in-depth community engagement to ensure our community is aligned on disaster preparedness. Drawing on the community's lived and perceived experiences, our organization was well-suited to highlight common concerns in the preparation for and aftermath of disasters here in the Southwest Houston area. Thus, by creating this report, we took community engagement seriously. **First, let's explore the desired outcomes from our work and the progress made in the community so far.**

Figure 2. AliefVotes Youth Conference on June 14, 2025, with more than 150+ attendees and 22+ tabling organizations. Organized by AliefVotes Events Managers and Associates (2025-2026 Term) Helin Wang, Katelyn Tieu, Cindy Ukwu, Kelly Ngo, their efforts truly encapsulated the youth spirit and engagement that was poured into the creation of this report.

DESIRED OUTCOMES

A "disaster event" refers to any natural, technological, or human-caused incident that disrupts normal community functions, overwhelms local response capacity, and necessitates coordinated emergency management efforts—including but not limited to hurricanes, flooding, severe storms, extreme heat, winter weather, wildfires, chemical releases, infrastructure failures, and public health emergencies. As such, our outcomes have been co-designed with stakeholders and revised by the Resilient Cities Network. You can view the Resilient Cities Network's Alief Plan at the following shortened link: tinyurl.com/alief-action-plan.

Goal: Strengthen community resilience to extreme weather events by empowering and organizing youth voices to lead and sustain collective action.

Desired Outcomes from our Efforts:

- Increased capacity and resources for youth-led organizations to create meaningful impact within their neighborhoods.
- Enhanced community awareness and preparedness for extreme weather events, ensuring greater readiness and resilience.
- Strengthened community infrastructure and enhanced neighborhood third spaces through pocket prairies and civic engagement.

Community Outputs from the Investment:

- AliefVotes' organizational capacity is enhanced through the development of new initiatives and the establishment of long-term partnerships and collaborations to sustain its activities and capacity-building efforts.
- Community connections are leveraged and strengthened through a series of events and workshops designed to raise awareness of extreme climate risks and enhance community engagement.
- Community third spaces, such as Alief Community Gardens and Pocket-Prairies, are improved through a coordinated and facilitated collaborative design process, fostering greater community involvement and shared ownership.

DEMOGRAPHICS

Situated in the fourth largest city in the nation, Alief is a neighborhood that is near the climate caused by the Gulf of Mexico, and our proximity to large bodies of water is a crucial component to the region's tropical storm and hurricane formation. Houston's population exceeds 2.3 million, and the larger metropolitan statistical area includes over 7.8 million residents. This report, and the focus of AliefVotes, is centered on the Alief community. Boasting over 112,672 residents, Alief represents one of the most diverse neighborhoods in the city.

The area is defined by the Alief Super Neighborhood Council to be bordered by Sam Houston Parkway to the east (also known as Beltway 8), West Bellfort Avenue and Keegan's Bayou in the south, Highway 6 to the West, and Westpark Tollway to the north (which has historically bifurcated the Alief community). The community dates back to 1861 as a flood-prone prairie called Dairy, 15 miles Southwest of the Brays Bayou headwaters. Alief, in the 1900s, was greatly affected by the Great Hurricane. In 1911, the Alief Independent School District was created and the area was annexed in 1977 by the City of Houston (Alief Super Neighborhood Council).

Figure 3. A drone snapshot of the iconic Alief water tower just north of West Park Tollway of the community.

Figure 4. Local gardeners working at the Alief Community Garden owned by Alief ISD and the International Management District.

Alief is housed in what’s historically been known as the “Forgotten District” in Houston City Council District F. Due to economic divestment, a lack of community engagement, and infrastructure gaps, Alief has been known as an underserved community. Today, the community is home to people of all ages and ethnicities—Nigerians, Chinese, Ethiopians, European-Americans, African Americans, Hispanics, Koreans, Japanese, El Salvadorans, Vietnamese, and many more. The neighborhood also includes Little Saigon, a Vietnamese enclave that boasts significant diversity and a range of small businesses and restaurants. Accordingly, 50% of residents are foreign-born, and over 90+ languages are spoken in the Alief community.

An essential factor in Alief’s history is the local economy and the neighborhood's backbone of small businesses. The average household income is lower in Alief than in the rest of the City, with Alief residents earning \$47,321 a year, while Houston residents generally earn \$60,440. 42% of the community is cost-burdened, spending 30% or more on basic household expenses, and 25% of the community is below the federal poverty line.

CLIMATE RISKS IN ALIEF

Alief is incredibly strong in its dynamism as a community, as we are a neighborhood where we show that no matter where you come from, you can have a chance of having a productive, passion-filled life. The multilingual and multicultural environment fosters a strong small-business environment, where neighbors can find enclaves of businesses, restaurants, and plazas that serve everyone. However, the community's geographic diversity presents unique challenges.

Flooding is a threat in Alief. First, Alief's flood risk is severe in some low-lying regions of the city, given that the neighborhood of Alief was built on a prairie. According to a quantitative analysis by First Street, 16,571 properties in the Alief area are at risk, representing 76.1% of all properties in the neighborhood. Over 80% of homes have a greater than 26% chance of being affected by flooding in the next 30 years, and approximately 60% of Alief is in FEMA's 100-year floodplain. With rising costs, residents can face the burden of home repairs, insurance, maintenance, and more. These effects are especially compounded by language barriers and a lack of resources from governmental agencies.

Figure 5. floodplain estimate map generated by the Resilient Cities Network team.

Second, according to the First Street report, Alief suffers from extreme heat. Alief is expected to have 7 days that exceed 110 degrees Fahrenheit this year. 100% of homes in the Alief area are already classified as having an extremely high heat risk. More broadly, 98% of homes in Houston face extreme heat risk, and the compounding effects of hot days and heatwaves can have a severe effect on residents, especially our most vulnerable seniors and residents with disabilities.

Figure 6. Alief land-use categorized in the community between industrial, commercial, residential, and more.

Finally, key findings from community members have identified the following results through outreach from 2021-2023 under the Climate Resilience Measurement for Communities Tool (CRMC), which utilized surveys and, most importantly, the community's lived experiences. The following pages discuss these findings.

DATA BACKED SURVEYS

The Climate Resilience Measurement for Communities (CRMC) survey polled 68% of respondents identified as female and 32% as male, with 22.7% in the 18-30 age group, 61% in the 31-65 age group, and 16% in the 65+ age group. The sample size was 75 household surveys, seven key informant interviews, and one focus group. Our September and December 2025 roundtables focused on the senior community, filling in relevant sampling gaps.

According to Resilience for Communities and its action plan, the key findings were particularly striking:

- 89% of respondents agree or strongly agree that heat waves are becoming more frequent. 83% say the same about flood risk.
- 64% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the community could take more action on climate change.
- 20% of respondents did not know if their homes were in a floodplain.
- 38.6% of respondents have had their property damaged two or more times by flooding in the last ten years.

In particular, grassroots outreach has led to the following community design priorities. If you are a stakeholder reading this report, these project ideas came directly from the community of Alief and are aggregated:

- Better roads with pedestrian safety and fewer potholes.
- Public safety concerns.
- More green infrastructure, like pocket prairies and tree plantings.
- Education programs for at-home repairs.
- Updating drainage systems in Alief.
- Solar panel installation programs.
- Increase of food pantries and community awareness.
- Work at the Alief Community Garden.
- Educational programs on Alternative Energy Use/Energy Efficiency.
- Retention Ponds.
- More greenery in general.

THE DEMAND EXISTS

Through disaster kit distribution, food distribution to seniors and residents with disabilities, and continuous high-demand workshops, we've seen that the need is there. Our rooms overflow, the signup sheets are enormous, and students are actively wanting to help their communities out. This protocol is also a dire showcase to government officials and their offices that Alief needs help. Furthermore, our collective efforts can be a national model and for other Houston neighborhoods facing severe issues.

Figure 7. Photos from senior food delivery on November 23, 2025, and disaster kit distributions where AliefVotes gave away over 100 disaster kits to Alief resilient. Unfortunately, we ran out of materials, and many more were expecting—a qualitative reflection of demand in the community for education, resources, and help.

Due to limited emergency communication in the language, Alief's high population, and lack of plans in some apartment complexes, we must do more. The following sections focus on community feedback, events organized, the disaster protocol, and policy recommendations.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

COMMUNITY FEEDBACK PHILOSOPHY

Alief is one of Houston’s most culturally and linguistically diverse neighborhoods. Along the Bellaire Boulevard corridor, residents from dozens of countries have built vibrant communities featuring sari shops, taquerías, African groceries, dim sum restaurants, mosques, churches, temples, and community centers serving speakers of Vietnamese, Spanish, Mandarin, Cantonese, Yoruba, Arabic, Urdu, and many other languages. This diversity is a significant strength but also creates challenges for emergency preparedness, requiring culturally competent and language-accessible planning. What better way to engage the community than to hear from them? Our community feedback is focused on grassroots outreach.

Figure 8. Photos across areas of Alief that showcase student leadership, such as the Alief Community Garden, Pocket Prairie, the local youth workshop at the Chinese Community Center, and a clean-up at Kerr High School.

HURRICANE BERYL AND ONGOING INFRASTRUCTURE CHALLENGES

When Hurricane Beryl struck Alief and the Greater Houston area in July 2024, it revealed that the same weaknesses exposed during Winter Storm Uri continue to affect the community. The storm was a reminder that while there have been improvements in emergency alerts and local cooperation, major gaps in infrastructure, communication, and equity remain. For Alief, Beryl was proof that the lessons of the past have not been fully learned and that residents continue to bear the burden of systemic neglect.

Figure 9. Graphics representing the geographical nature and approximate timeline of Hurricane Beryl in 2024.

Hurricane Beryl made landfall in Texas on July 8, 2024, as a Category One storm with sustained winds of 80 miles per hour. According to the National Weather Service, more than 2.3 million of CenterPoint Energy’s 2.6 million customers lost power across the Houston area, leaving large portions of Harris County without electricity for over twenty-four hours. The Houston Chronicle reported that sixty percent of Harris County customers were affected, and some neighborhoods faced outages lasting nearly a week. These power losses occurred as temperatures climbed above one hundred degrees Fahrenheit, creating dangerous heat conditions that turned power restoration into a matter of survival.

The Guardian reported that more than 1.7 million Texans were still without electricity three days after the storm, with heat-related illnesses rising sharply across the region.

In Alief, these outages disrupted every aspect of daily life. Without reliable electricity, families faced challenges maintaining food safety, storing medications, and communicating with loved ones. For many, the most challenging part was not knowing when power would return. Utility company websites and phone lines provided conflicting updates, leaving residents anxious and uncertain about whether to stay home, throw away spoiled food, or seek shelter elsewhere. The confusion highlighted how critical accurate communication is during disasters and how much more work is needed to keep communities informed.

Hurricanes may come and go during a particular season, but they will always be around. We can never fully predict when Mother Nature hits. That's why it's essential to bring community members together to ensure that we have as much information and action as possible.

Figure 10. Disaster recovery efforts led by City Councilwoman Tiffany D. Thomas' Office of District F in the aftermath of Beryl.

ALIEF'S DISASTER PROTOCOL

With every community, there must be a unique plan for recovery, response, and disaster preparation. While this protocol is not perfect, it proposes a clear structure to address various phases of disaster management and unique challenges to consider here in Alief: preparedness, response, recovery, and mitigation. In each of these sections, we will outline a desired objective, activities and actions that can lead to that goal, and opportunities to support in that space.

Figure 11. Student-led workshops in Alief define the mission and purpose of AliefVotes.

1: PREPAREDNESS

Preparedness is all that is needed before disaster strikes. In Alief, a localized protocol must be inclusive of our immigrant-rich community—culturally appropriate foods, copies of immigration documents, and perhaps medications and paperwork for our seniors in multi-generational households. So, the preparedness section will be central to what residents of any background can do to prepare for incoming disasters. Whether it's a hurricane or tropical storm, Alief neighbors must be prepared with a useful emergency kit, brief their family members on evacuation routes and the location of essential documents, establish hyperlocal neighborhood communication systems through Homeowners Associations, Nextdoor, or Civic Clubs, and engage in public education campaigns through the school district itself before an active hurricane season. Furthermore, registration of emergency alerts such as AlertHouston and Ready Harris and ethnic media (WhatsApp groups, WeChat) play an essential role as well. **As you are preparing for disasters, feel free to follow this list to ensure you have your bases covered.**

1.1: EMERGENCY KITS

Figure 12. An example of what a disaster preparation kit could look like for an Alief family.

The first step to preparation is to ensure that all residents have tangible emergency kits. Each household could aim to maintain supplies for at least 72 hours without power (or even longer during Winter Storm Uri), water, and outside assistance. It's best to plan for a week or even more. The following page will include a comprehensive list informed by recommendations for a basic emergency kit, with considerations specific to Alief, including winter storms, extreme heat, culturally cognizant considerations, and considerations for our residents of senior status.

For an easy-to-use resource list, please see the end of this report. The following pages are comprehensive, so the easy-to-use resource list is accordingly categorized for family use.

BASIC EMERGENCY KIT FOR 72-HOUR MINIMUM:

- 1 gallon of water per person per day for drinking and sanitation (minimum 3 gallons per person, ideally 7 gallons).
- A full bathtub (if you have one) before disaster strikes.
- Non-perishable stock requiring no cooking that includes goods like canned items, peanut butter, crackers, and ready-to-eat meals.
- Butane burner for cooking, if needed in more extended outages.
- Manual can opener.
- Flashlights and extra batteries (at least two flashlights, and ensure that your family knows of their placement).
- A battery-powered or hand-crank radio for emergency broadcasts.
- First aid kit with bandages, antiseptics, and pain relievers.
- 7-day supply of all prescriptions plus copies of prescriptions (brief those that you take care of, especially).
- Cell phone chargers, like portable battery packs and car chargers.
- Cash: \$200-500 in small bills (ATMs and card readers can fail during outages).
- Important documents in a waterproof container that include, at a minimum, your IDs, insurance policies, medical records, immigration documents, property deeds, and vehicle titles.
- Toilet paper, hand sanitizer, soap, feminine products, and diapers.
- Whistle to signal for help.
- Rain gear, rain shoes, long pants, and gloves for repairs.
- Infant formula for newborns, mess kits, and paper disposable utensils.
- Fire extinguishers and waterproofed matches.
- Dust masks and plastic sheeting for sheltering in place (optional).
- Wrench or pliers to turn off utilities.
- Escape tools for your car.
- Moist towels, garbage bags, and disinfectants for sanitation.
- Plastic tarps for any emergency roof repairs.
- Local maps, if you have them.
- Toothpaste, toothbrushes, wet wipes, and snacks.
- Mobile and laptop chargers in various locations.
- An easy-to-understand meeting place for your family.

ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS (OTHER HAZARDS)

- Plywood or hurricane shutters, tarps, duct tape, rope for fast repairs.
- Battery-powered fans, cooling towels, and electrolyte packets during extended heat waves.
- Food, water, and necessary medical items for your pets.
- Extra blankets, warm clothing layers, and pipe insulation tape.
- Knowledge of how to shut off your water main.
- Food, water, medications, carrier, vaccination records, and ID tags for your pets.
- Store non-perishable versions of culturally appropriate foods (halal, kosher, vegetarian options available at Hong Kong Market, 99 Ranch, H-Mart on Bellaire, Fiesta).
- Stock of prayer items, religious texts, or spiritual comfort items.
- Copies of immigration documents, visas, green cards, and work permits with your emergency documents in a waterproof bag.
- Emergency contact information written in your native language and especially provided to family members who do not speak English. You may even elect to do an audio version for them.
- Apply for Centerpoint's Chronic Condition or Critical Care Residential Customer Status at 713-207-2222.
- Register with STEAR (State of Texas Emergency Assistance Registry): 211texas.org/stear or call 2-1-1.
- Have backup batteries or a generator plan for life-sustaining equipment.
- Keep a written list of all medical equipment, medications, and dosages.
- Know the location of the nearest hospital and dialysis center.
- Have a manual wheelchair if you use a powered one.
- Store extra supplies: catheters, oxygen, feeding supplies, etc.
- Keep an emergency kit in your car: water bottles, non-perishable snacks, phone charger (car adapter), blanket, flashlight, basic first aid, jumper cables.
- Take photos of all important documents and email them to yourself or store them in the cloud (Google Drive, iCloud, Dropbox).
- Photograph every room in your home and all valuable possessions for insurance purposes before the disaster strikes.

1.2: DOING YOUR RESEARCH

Knowledge is power. Understanding your surroundings can go a long way toward helping you identify risks. For instance, many Alief residents don't realize they live in a floodplain. You can enter your Alief address and view your specific flood risk using the [Harris County Flood Education Mapping Tool](http://harriscountyfemt.org) at harriscountyfemt.org. You can also layer your knowledge with drainage networks with the Harris County Flood Control District (hcfcd.org) and FEMA's Flood Map Service Center at msc.fema.gov. Many Alief residents live near Brays or Keegan Bayou. They could pay special attention to the condition of the bayous, as drainage and water conveyance are essential to mitigation.

Figure 13. Harris County Mapping for 100-Year and 500-Year Floodplains in Alief, Texas.

Hold on, what is the difference between a 100-year floodplain and a 500-year floodplain? A 100-year floodplain has a 1% chance of flooding in any given year, while a 500-year floodplain has a 0.2% chance of flooding in any given year. Accordingly, the 100-year floodplain is the "base flood" and is considered a high-risk area. In contrast, the 500-year floodplain represents an area of lower but still significant risk.

UNDERSTANDING FLOOD ZONE RISK

Ultimately, understanding your flood zone helps you to figure out the likelihood of evacuating during heavy rain events, if you need flood insurance (you do, if you live on a floodplain like many Alief neighbors do), and to know how high water rise might affect your house and thus where to store your items at your home.

Standard homeowners or renters insurance does not cover flooding. You could know that flood insurance is separate and has a 30-day waiting period, so you may not be able to purchase it while a storm is approaching. This is to prevent insurance companies from facing a surge of costly claims that destabilize the insurance system. Flood insurance is not free, and you must pay for it. However, it can be critical because flood insurance covers direct physical damage to your home and belongings from a flood, including the building's structure, foundation, electrical and plumbing systems, and permanent fixtures. It also covers personal property, such as furniture, electronics, and clothing.

You can find avenues to purchase flood insurance at the following:

- National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP) at [floodsmart.gov](https://www.floodsmart.gov).
- [Private flood insurance may offer better rates.](#)
- Renters can and could get flood insurance (often \$50-100/year).
- Even if you're not in a mapped floodplain, consider it anyway!

For most Alief renters, your landlord's insurance does not cover your personal belongings. Renters insurance:

- Typically costs \$15-30 per month.
- Covers personal property (furniture, electronics, clothing, etc.).
- Provides liability coverage.
- May cover temporary housing costs if your unit is uninhabitable.
- Available from most major insurance companies.

It is always better to be safe than sorry. When disaster strikes, having flood insurance can be a massive relief for families. However, the affordability crisis is creating an ever-increasing gap for many families who are unable to purchase flood insurance for their families. To lower costs, policyholders can implement risk-reducing measures like elevating their home, installing flood openings, or raising utilities.

1.3: UNDERSTANDING LANGUAGES

Our community is unique because Alief speaks over 90 languages. Everyone deserves to understand and cognize emergency information. In Alief, we've seen prominent language use of English, Spanish, Vietnamese, Chinese (Traditional, Simplified, and Dialects), Arabic, Yoruba, Hindi, Urdu, Burmese, Korean, Tagalog, French, Nepali, Bengali, Gujarati, Swahili, Amharic, and more. Thus, in any dissemination of critical information around disasters, whether it's the location of shelters or updates from CenterPoint on when utilities may be restored, it must be accessible in language.

There is a significant amount of services available, but more can be done in the language accessibility space. For example, HOPE Clinic provides services in 30+ languages and can assist with health-related interpretation services, in which residents can call 713-773-0803. YMCA International Services has multilingual staff at 713-758-9280. Other resources include Alief ISD's family and community engagement department, which can support school-based distribution, and BakerRipley Gulfton-Sharpstown Campus, which has multilingual community navigators.

Thus, it is essential for all government stakeholders, whether elected or not, to maintain a roster of volunteers willing to translate flyers and community resources. Faith institutions often have members who can interpret, so it's critical to coordinate with mosques, temples, churches, and gurdwaras before disaster strikes. Youth can also leverage their skills to ensure that their families, who may not all speak English as their first language, are taken care of.

1.4: COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

One challenge that arises in disaster preparation is effective communication. Residents with students in Alief ISD could ensure they contact the public relations and family and community engagement departments through the district's central office. Knowing how to navigate sites such as Schoology for school-related updates, navigate student transportation, and use schools as recovery sites is also of great importance. Furthermore, many channels for reaching English-speaking populations are cable TV in Alief (ABC 13, KTRK, KPRC). Still, communities and neighborhoods could be prepared in partnership with ethnic media. English media could also actively partner and work with the following, non-exhaustive ethnic media partners:

- U.S. Chinese Channel AM1050, HUM FM 103.5, La Voz Houston, Telemundo, Que Onda, Radio Saigon (900 AM), the Chinese Times, Arab Voices, Afrocentrik Television, Afrovibes TV, Indo American News, and Masala Radio 98.7 FM, Univision Radio Houston, Saigon Radio, VietTV Houston, Southern Chinese Daily, World Journal Houston, WeChat public accounts, and Whatsapp groups.

Social media and messaging apps are also primary communication tools, with WhatsApp used in some Hispanic, South Asian, and African communities. WeChat is used by Chinese-speaking residents. Facebook groups include Alief community groups such as the Alief Super Neighborhood Council, which are also tied to Nextdoor for neighborhood-specific alerts, and even Telegram for younger immigrants.

Therefore, working with all platforms in advance is a vital disaster preparedness technique. Stakeholders must also partner with apartment complex managers and seniors, as well as with ethnic grocery stores like Hong Kong Market, H-Mart, Fiesta, Indian/Pakistani Grocers, and Nigerian Grocers, to post flyers and make announcements. Yard signs at major intersections indicating centers, water distribution dates, and phone numbers useful for recovery are also helpful.

1.5: COMMUNITY DRILLS & ALERTS

Communities are stronger with helpful neighbors. Alief HOAs and civic clubs could help build block networks by proactively identifying a list of neighbors, especially those who are senior/disabled, who may need some extra help. Exchange contact information and identify houses with generators, medical training, language skills, and perhaps trucks for evacuation. It's also important to designate meeting points, such as schools. Say, you live at Ashford Terrace. Youngblood Intermediate may be a good option, but Hackberry Park is not necessarily a good option, as it also serves as a detention pond. Apartment complex residents could also join group chats, know their manager's emergency contacts, and request post-emergency information from management in many languages.

1.6: CRITICAL RESOURCES

On top of community-led drills and practices, the following resources below are critical to ensure that residents are alerted on major updates.

- Alert Houston: houstonemergency.org/alerts
- Ready Harris: Text "Ready" to (281) 609-9093 or ReadyHarris.org/SignUp
- For residents who need evacuation or medical assistance: STEAR at stear.texas.gov or call 2-1-1
- Alief ISD: Through your child's school enrollment to be notified of school closures and district emergencies. You can also monitor their district social media pages on Facebook and Instagram.

Figure 14. Alief ISD facilities and Dr. Anthony Mays play crucial leadership roles in ensuring that families are informed.

2: RESPONSE

Building on Precinct 4 and District F's investments and looking ahead, the community must also respond by responsibly communicating live updates, as many languages are not covered in local media's live reports. Cooling and warming centers must be up and running, ADA accessible, pet-friendly, and staffed by multilingual personnel. These centers must coordinate in advance with the Houston Food Bank and local providers, such as the Harris Center, to ensure that those with mental health and medical needs are safe. Finally, generator safety must be central to any awareness campaign and update—during disasters, especially winter storms, residents are at heightened risk of carbon monoxide poisoning, particularly those who are most vulnerable and without nearby family members. This chapter focuses on the government and community responses to disasters in Alief.

2.1: CITY ADVOCACY

Representation matters. It's essential for our local representatives, no matter who is in office, to advocate for equitable distribution of emergency resources. Whether it's Harris County Precinct 4, District F, media outlets, or the Office of Emergency Management, all stakeholders must have Alief in mind to ensure that our community is taken care of.

- **Houston OEM:** houstonemergency.org, 713-884-4500
- **Harris County OEM:** ReadyHarris.org
- **District F Council Office:** 832-393-3002
- **Harris County Precinct 4:** 832-927-4444
- Call **3-1-1** for City of Houston services and to report needs such as debris removal, red light outages, and to find resources.

2.2: EMERGENCY ALERTS

And once disasters hit, we must shift our focus to response. Response encapsulates the period from imminent disaster to immediate aftermath. For Alief, this means local officials are ensuring that emergency resources, such as open multi-service centers and debris pickup vehicles, are activated on the Westside. Historically, storing and securing ice has been difficult, requiring advanced preparation. The community must also respond by communicating live updates responsibly, as many languages are not covered in the local media's live reports. Cooling and warming centers must be up and running, ADA accessible, include pet-friendly options, and be staffed by multilingual staff. Centers must also previously coordinate with the Houston Food Bank and local centers, such as the Harris Center, to ensure that those with mental health and medical needs are safe. Finally, generator safety must be central to any awareness campaign and update. During disasters, especially winter storms, residents are at risk of carbon monoxide poisoning, especially those who are most vulnerable and without family members.

There must be a proactive activation protocol, where community members and stakeholders translate key information as it comes into common languages such as Spanish, Vietnamese, Chinese, Arabic, Yoruba, and more within 5 hours. Communities could share information via WhatsApp and WeChat, and contact ethnic media partners for broadcast. Message contents could include: What is happening (storms, floods, freeze), what residents could do NOW, location of nearest shelters (such as the Alief Neighborhood Center and Tracy Gee Community Center), emergency phone numbers, and who to contact for what (311 and 211) and ethnic media tunes-ins for FM and AM radio.

Figure 15. "On Air" graphic to showcase the importance of radio and telecommunications in disaster response.

2.3: COOLING & HEATING SHELTERS

Depending on the disaster, governmental entities are sure to open cooling or heating shelters. Whether it's a hurricane, winter freeze, or heat wave, the following centers have usually been open in the community. However, this information changes from disaster to disaster, and one must consult the most up-to-date information: Alief Neighborhood Center, YMCA International Services, and the Tracy Gee Community Center. Historically, Church Without Walls – Eldridge and Piney Point Elementary School has also served as a storage site for food, water, oxygen tanks, blankets, and other items contributed by external partners. Each ERT lead will prepare inventory reports and confirm volunteers to serve as distribution centers.

A great contact to have during disasters is 1-800-RED-CROSS (733-2767) or at redcross.org. Residents can also call 311 to ensure they receive the most up-to-date information on official city and county services.

During emergencies, Alief neighbors are encouraged to also call 3-1-1 to confirm which locations are open and operating hours and at times, there are free transportation to cooling/heating centers available through 3-1-1 and METRO. During these visits, do not forget to bring medications, phone charger, identification, and comfort items. Always call ahead to confirm pet policies and ensure that your furry ones are taken care of. The next few pages will discuss critical centers in and near Alief.

Figure 16. Alief Neighborhood Center serves as one of the most important central locations for disaster recovery and distribution.

OVERVIEW: MULTI-SERVICE CENTERS

Multi-service centers serve as critical community infrastructure for emergency response by providing centralized locations for emergency shelter, resource distribution, service coordination, and community support during disasters while building on existing community facilities and relationships that residents trust and can access easily.

The **Tracy Gee Community Center** at 3599 Westcenter Drive serves as a primary multi-service center with ample meeting spaces that can accommodate emergency shelter for 100+ residents, commercial kitchen facilities for emergency food preparation and distribution, backup power generation capability for essential services during power outages, accessible facilities for residents with disabilities, and existing programming relationships with diverse community organizations that can be leveraged for emergency response coordination. Typically, the center opens as a cooling/heating site and conducts various food distributions. While this location is slightly out of Alief, the intense programming that the center holds is quite valuable.

Figure 17. Front photo of the Tracy Gee Community Center, managed by Harris County Precinct 4.

The **Alief Neighborhood Center** at 11903 Bellaire Boulevard provides additional emergency shelter capacity with multiple meeting rooms that can be configured for family emergency housing, fitness facilities that can serve as additional shelter space during large-scale emergencies, senior programming spaces that are familiar to elderly residents who may need emergency assistance, parking facilities that can accommodate emergency service vehicles and community resource distribution, and central location accessibility through public transportation on the #2 line. The center is historic as it combines many city departments together, and the inclusion of a generator in the upcoming years will allow this center to be a haven for many.

Figure 18. Front photo of the Alief Neighborhood Center (formerly the Alief Community Center) on South Kirkwood and Bellaire Boulevard, managed by the City of Houston.

The **Chinese Community Center** at 9800 Town Park Drive offers culturally specific emergency services for Chinese families with multilingual staff capable of providing emergency assistance in Mandarin and Cantonese, cultural competency for addressing family emergency decision-making and cultural requirements, and community relationships that enable effective outreach to Chinese residents who may not access other emergency services. These meeting spaces can serve as an emergency shelter with culturally appropriate arrangements and community kitchen facilities for emergency food preparation that accommodate dietary requirements. AliefVotes often either organizes workshops at the Chinese Community Center (reaching the east portion of Alief) or at the Alief Neighborhood Center (reaching the more central portion of the community).

Figure 19. Front photo of the Chinese Community Center on Town Park and Corporate Drive in the East Alief region.

Religious institutions throughout Alief represent a critical but underutilized disaster response asset with unique capabilities that complement traditional emergency shelters. Church Without Walls on Eldridge exemplifies how faith communities can serve as distributed emergency response centers, offering not only physical facilities but also deep community relationships that enable effective outreach to specific populations during disasters. These institutions possess established trust with diverse linguistic and religious communities, fellowship halls and classrooms suitable for emergency housing, commercial kitchen facilities for large-scale food preparation and distribution, and pastoral care services that address the spiritual and emotional trauma accompanying disasters.

Unlike conventional emergency shelters that focus primarily on basic needs, religious institutions can provide culturally competent care that respects dietary restrictions, language preferences, and religious practices while offering familiar spaces where residents feel safe and supported.

Figure 20. Church without Walls represents an important community gathering location and trust-building institution.

2.4: FOOD & WATER DISTRIBUTION

One major obstacle that arises after disasters is the need for food and water distributions, especially for community members who rely on SNAP benefits and our most vulnerable citizens. The following are organizations that have historically organized food distributions during disasters, with leading partners such as Houston City Council District F, led by Councilwoman Tiffany D. Thomas.

Additional contacts include Houston Food Bank at 713-223-3700 and houstonfoodbank.org, which serves as a central hub where organizations coordinate most emergency food distribution. Local faith institutions: Many mosques, churches, and temples distribute food during emergencies. Again, as with shelters and cooling/heating sites, these vary from disaster to disaster due to resource allocation challenges and opportunities. It is essential to call both 211 and 311 to ensure you have the most up-to-date information on food distributions. Historically, ice has been challenging to gather after an emergency, so be prepared, Alief.

What to Expect at Distribution Sites:

- Lines can be long (especially if you are in a car)—bring water, shade, and patience. If you are coming by foot, know that some sites may not allow that, and also have a way to carry your goods.
- Most sites provide water, ice, tarps, and shelf-stable food. It depends on the organization and the resources available.
- Some require ID or proof of address; many do not.
- Hours vary—check ReadyHarris.org or call 2-1-1 for current information.
- Always look towards WHAM, or West Houston Assistance Ministries. They often lead in disaster preparedness and distributions.

Whether you are a community non-profit in Alief or resident, you can:

- Push for distribution sites WITHIN Alief.
- Request Houston Food Bank mobile pantry deployments to apartment complexes and senior homes.
- Coordinate with faith institutions to serve as distribution points.
- Ensure distribution announcements go out in multiple languages.

COMMON DISTRIBUTION LOCATIONS IN ALIEF

Food security during disasters requires systematic planning that meets immediate hunger needs and long-term food access challenges while respecting Alief’s cultural and religious diversity. Families face economic strain when their regular access to food is disrupted. Community members described severe food loss during extended power outages, such as one resident who lost “\$500 worth of frozen food” during Winter Storm Uri. Effective emergency food planning must therefore address both emergency meal distribution and post-disaster food assistance for households that experience significant losses.

Figure 21. Community-led food distributions across Alief represented residents coming together to help our families.

Alief’s emergency food distribution networks could build on existing community resources, including the Houston Food Bank’s partnerships, West Houston Assistance Ministries’ pantry programs, and the many food distribution services provided by churches, mosques, temples, and community gardens. These networks already have trusted relationships within specific cultural and linguistic communities and can coordinate culturally appropriate food distribution during emergencies. Community-controlled systems are more effective than external, temporary relief efforts because they leverage existing trust, local knowledge, and volunteer capacity. On the following page are examples of food distribution networks.

AS OF PUBLICATION: FOOD DISTRIBUTION SITES

No one could go hungry. Thus, this report aims to inform Alief residents and stakeholders about the who's who of food distribution in the community. Note that as of this publication date in the fall of 2025, the information is accurate. Thus, do not rely on this information past this period without first verifying with the community leaders through the contact information below.

West Houston Assistance Ministries (WHAM)

- West Houston Assistance Ministries (WHAM) provides large-scale food distributions, emergency groceries, and essential supplies to families across Alief, including SNAP recipients and households experiencing hardship. They offer both drive-thru and walk-up services and frequently partner with Harris County and local nonprofits during periods of high need. WHAM is known for serving thousands of families monthly with fresh produce, pantry staples, and household necessities.
- Address: 10501 Meadowglen Ln., Houston, TX 77042
- Phone: 713-977-7803
- Website: www.whamministries.org/food-pantry

The WOW Project – Food Haven at the Alief Community Garden

- The WOW Project's Food Haven pantry focuses on providing healthy, free food options on most Sundays while reducing food waste by rescuing produce and groceries from restaurants, farms, and local stores. They distribute nutritious fruits, vegetables, and other food items and operate additional programs such as Houston Healthiest Pantry and Gather Grow Give, promoting sustainable, community-based food access.
- Address: 8409 1/2 Dairy View Ln., Houston, TX 77072
- Email: jabelle.lipscomb@thewowproject.org
- Website: <https://www.thewowproject.org/>

Tzu Chi Foundation – Southern Region

- Tzu Chi Foundation provides monthly community food distributions in Southwest Houston and partners with local organizations to supply families with fresh produce, pantry goods, and disaster-relief items. Their distributions are volunteer-driven and open to all families in need, prioritizing compassion and dignity in service.
- Address: 6200 Corporate Dr., Houston, TX 77036
- Email: southerncharity@tzuchi.us
 - Additional Contacts: joyce.lin@us.tzuchi.org & roger_lin@tzuchi.us

E.L. Kingsley Foundation

- The E.L. Kingsley Foundation hosts community-based food distributions at AGAPA Christian Fellowship Church, providing groceries, produce, and pantry bags to families in Alief and Mission Bend. They focus on community service, volunteerism, and faith-based support for local households facing food insecurity.
- Distribution Location: AGAPA Christian Fellowship Church, 8400 Boone Rd., Houston, TX 77072
- Phone: 346-888-7300
- Email: kingsleyfoundation1@gmail.com

Houston Food Bank – Partner Distributions

- The Houston Food Bank partners with churches, apartment complexes, and nonprofits across the Alief/SW Houston area to provide free groceries, produce, and emergency food assistance. Services are always free, with no income or paperwork required at most partner locations.
- Website: houstonfoodbank.org
- General Assistance Line: 713-223-3700

Figure 22. Various photos from community engagement and food/water distribution sessions.

2.5: GENERATORS

Power outages, especially in some Alief grids, will be widespread. As neighbors, please remind each other to never run generators indoors or in enclosed spaces. This also goes to running your car with your garage closed during winter storms. Ensure that you use heavy-duty extension cords, that you do not refuel while the machine is hot, and keep them away from windows and doors.

2.6: MEDICATIONS

For medications, you must have the contact information for local health care services and call 911 for life-threatening emergencies. Know your primary physician, dentist, and doctors, and when they will be scheduled to open. Some helpful health-related numbers to have on hand are the Harris Center 24/7 Crisis Line at 713-970-7000, the 988 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline (call or text 988), and the Mobile Crisis Outreach Team (MCOT), which is dispatched through 713-970-7000. If you lose medications in a disaster, contact your pharmacy as emergency refills are often available.

Figure 23. Grid infrastructure example to showcase the importance of reliable connection.

3: RECOVERY

After the response, there is recovery: a long, complicated process of rebuilding neighborhoods and families. This could look like connecting residents with the most up-to-date, in-language resources for FEMA individual assistance, applying for SBA loans, and understanding how to navigate local housing repair programs, while being honest about the speed and efficiency of these programs. Oftentimes, we see housing as the biggest recovery challenge, where the community could always benefit from more funding for single-family home repair, apartment complex restoration, and multilingual application resources.

Furthermore, residents must be proactively protected against malicious exploitation, such as contractor fraud or scams, in the wake of disasters. Residents could not need to pay upfront, verify licensing, or get multiple estimates in a vulnerable time. Especially with the prevalence of mold, remediation must be completed as early as possible for one's health. Finally, for immigrant families, neighbors must be informed of key messages, such as that FEMA does not share information with immigration enforcement and that many programs that serve residents do so regardless of status, such as Catholic Charities, BakerRipley, and YMCA.

Figure 24. A city view of the City Hall Annex and downtown in the background in the aftermath of Harvey.

3.1: ASSISTANCE & RESOURCES

Critically important is ensuring that your family is safeguarded. One avenue to do so is to repair damage to housing, whether from flooding, burst pipes, or other causes. Single-family home repair is often supplemented through FEMA's individual assistance, which is typically available after disasters at [DisasterAssistance.gov](https://www.DisasterAssistance.gov) or by calling 800-621-3362 within 60 days of the disaster declaration. People with speech or hearing impairments may call toll-free TTY at 1-800-462-7585. For small business owners, SBA Disaster Loans are Low-interest loans for homeowners and renters and can be applied for through sba.gov/disaster.

The City of Houston often has programs in the aftermath of disasters (which may take a while, fair warning) that support housing repairs, such as after Winter Storm Uri, Hurricane Beryl, and the Derecho. Ensure you visit the correct sites and contact the City of Houston Housing & Community Development at 832-394-6200 for home repair programs to learn more about what is currently available.

For those living in apartment complexes, tenants have rights, and Landlords must make repairs or allow lease termination. Some helpful resources include the Texas Tenant Advisor Hotline at [texastenant.org](https://www.texastenant.org) and Lone Star Legal Aid: 800-733-8394 for tenant rights assistance. Make sure that you document all damage with photos and written communication to the landlord (in any medium). The American Red Cross may also offer emergency financial assistance at 800-733-2767. For immigrant-inclusive resources, a great option is YMCA International Services, which can be reached at 713-758-9280; its staff specializes in refugee and immigrant services. Many state and local programs serve all residents regardless of status, and be sure to document everything by keeping records of all disaster damage and assistance applications.

4: MITIGATION

In the final stage stands mitigation—the discussion of how Alief can reduce future risk through sustained advocacy and error prevention. This could mean advocating for more detention basins, drainage improvements, and community-led green infrastructure projects, such as rain gardens and pocket prairies. Individual education on flood insurance navigation, understanding flood zones, and elevating appliances and electrical systems can go a long way as well. Generators must be fully equipped at the Alief Neighborhood Center, and affordable housing repair must always be top of mind for city and county officials. Finally, strengthening community response mechanisms, such as the neighborhood network and CERT volunteer training, will provide a stable foundation and ensure that Alief is ready for the next disaster. As a youth-run organization, we strongly encourage residents to lean on their families, teenagers, and children to help navigate language barriers, communication challenges, and physical exertion through volunteerism, ensuring that all neighbors are cared for.

Mitigation can look like advocating for flood control district investments in Alief watersheds, green infrastructure construction in the community, ensuring your neighbors are clearing out your drainage systems, advocating to your Houston City Council for Capital Improvement Program Priorities to include generators at community centers (one is on the way for the Alief Neighborhood Center), advocating for more funds to be allocated to housing repair when allocated by the city of Houston, push for tenant rights by speaking with your landlord, and building upon your robust community resilience networks through mutual aid, multilingual outreach, and training for community members. Remember, the more we can do, the more prepared we will be as a community.

Finally, part of mitigation is policy advocacy, which will be touched on in the final pages of this report, where policy recommendations stemming from community feedback can be considered and advocated for in subsequent Legislative sessions, Congresses, City Hall meetings, and more.

KEY ACCOMPLISHMENTS

To reach our goals, AliefVotes students and Alief ISD students engaged in serious community engagement through various projects. From community engagement roundtables to two comprehensive pocket-prairie projects, AliefVotes led an innovative effort to take steps toward our bold vision goal and desired outcomes, as prescribed on the prior page. At the heart of our work is deep collaboration with stakeholders, community members, and partners. The following few pages detail our efforts and events in chronological order.

COMMUNITY RESILIENT ALIEF WORKSHOPS

The Resilient Cities Network ultimately invested \$125,000 in the Alief community, executed through AliefVotes. But with every investment, there comes a story. Even before AliefVotes was involved in disaster preparedness work, Resilient Cities Network’s international team worked hard to identify community feedback for resilience to inform ultimate goals and community initiatives. The group identified Alief as a vibrant and diverse community, home to a wide range of stakeholders and organizations that collaborate to drive impactful projects. The Resilience for Communities program began in 2021 with the Resilient Cities Network, Z-Zurich, and Zurich Insurance. The initiative is global, as seen in the figure below.

Figure 25. Map showcasing Resilient Cities Network’s global reach. R-Cities has a portfolio in the United States and Alief.

The Resilient Cities Network aimed to understand better risks and vulnerabilities and the status of resilience of cities using the Climate Resilience Measurement for Communities (CRMC) tool which measures community perceptions of local shocks and stresses; Enhance equitable City, community and stakeholder engagement through prioritizing community participation, thus fostering the collaborative development of resilience solutions; Build local capacity through innovative tools and processes and technical assistance; and Drive investment and resources towards community resilience solutions developed with, and by, local stakeholders. Their outreach focused on three phases: Onboarding & Engagement, City Diagnostics, and Project Identification and Preparation. This process ranged from September 2023 to December 2025. **This report thus focuses on the entire process of investment identification and the youth-led execution of all projects.**

We hope you can come!

Listen to how your neighbors cope with floods and extreme heat

Share ideas and help choose the best solution for Alief to invest **\$125,000**

We are listening

Let's create projects that strengthen the community and Alief.

R4C Identify. Understand. Act.

Where? Alief Multi Service Center: 11903 Bellaire Blvd. Houston, Texas 77072-2310

When?

- Monday, September 25, 2023 at 5:30-8 pm
- Thursday, September 28, 2023, 5:30 pm-8pm

Contact: jvasquez@resilientcitiesnetwork.org

The first opportunity presented itself on September 25th and September 28th of 2023 at the Alief Neighborhood Center in Bellaire. With a new neighborhood center, Jordana Vasquez and the team approached Alief with a grassroots approach and listened to Alief community members. Their feedback ultimately guided the creation of this protocol through feedback, event planning, and execution of what community members identified as issues in disaster preparation and planning in Southwest Houston.

Figure 26. First resilient cities network workshop in September 2023 at the Alief Neighborhood Center.

The first workshop was transformational, sparking new initiatives in the Alief community. Through deep conversations, breakout tables, countless maps, and various outreach methods, the aggregated concerns in Alief stemming from community engagement were: reducing heat risk, increasing energy affordability, and increasing food accessibility. Before these workshops, data were collected in Alief at the WIC clinic, Motherland African Food Market, Hong Kong Food Markets, and soccer games from October & November 2022 to January 2023. Seven informational interviews were collected from Houston Public Works, the Office of Emergency Management, the Mayor's Office, and more. Focus groups of 15 participants were conducted at these workshops that focused on 76 indicators linked to resilience, climate shocks, and stresses.

Figure 27. Pictured are community stakeholders and neighbors at the community workshop, including the late Barbara Quattro, Alan Steinberg, Yaneth Calderon, and more.

The Alief community engagement process, according to the Resilient Cities Network report, revealed a predominantly female respondent base (67.7%) with most participants aged 31-65. The respondents are from a lower-income demographic, with nearly 30% earning below \$20,000 annually, and the majority fall within the \$20,000-\$40,000 range. The community is characterized by significant immigration patterns, with 94% of residents having moved to Alief and over half living there for 5-20 years, suggesting substantial population turnover possibly linked to immigration and economic mobility.

While 44.8% of respondents of our surveys don't identify as belonging to minority groups, the remaining population represents diverse ethnic (25%), religious (12.6%), and racial (9.2%) minorities, with employment spanning indoor work (37.3%), semi-indoor occupations (20%), and outdoor jobs (12%). Climate-related extreme events significantly impact this vulnerable community: 73% experience flood-related property damage, and 39% suffer multiple flood events, leading to prolonged financial recovery periods beyond one year for nearly 20% of residents.

Extreme heat poses an even greater challenge, affecting 79% of respondents during the worst heat events of the past decade and forcing adaptive behaviors such as staying with friends or family (44%), seeking cool spaces (19%), or enduring financial hardship (21%).

Figure 28. Collected data and aggregated results for the Alief community's perception of flooding impacts and extreme heat events.

All in all, based on these community feedback meetings, Alief residents discussed: a lack of civic investment, low voting propensity, low investment, the need for tree plantings, retention ponds, better drainage, awareness campaigns, financial concerns, green infrastructure, food support, and community gardens.

If you are interested in learning more and reading the entire community workshop process, you can read it at tinyurl.com/alief-design-sprint.

Figure 29. Community photo after the Resilient Cities Network workshops at the new Alief Neighborhood Center. Pictured on the very left is our very own AliefVotes fellow, Frank Cruz.

*“We are honored to receive this grant, which will deepen our efforts in building equity and resilience within the Alief community,” said Ny’Elle Blount, Director of Data & Records at AliefVotes and Alief Taylor student. “Through collaborative and intentional workshops focused on disaster preparedness, environmental justice, and other pressing issues, **we create spaces where residents can engage, learn, and act.**”*

Figure 30. Community members and government officials are coming together to provide grass-roots feedback during the workshop. Participants in the Design Sprints evaluated which of the identified resilience gaps were neighborhood priorities and would be carried forward into the solution design phase.

COMMUNITY CLEAN-UPS

Part of resilience comes from clean, beautiful communities. With our work in resilience, AliefVotes, and our partners often worked with organizations such as the Alief Super Neighborhood Council, Houston City Council Member Tiffany D. Thomas, Alief ISD, and SEWA International to empower students with fundamental organizing skills while also clearing areas that need urgent help. In the wake of solid waste delays, recycling concerns, and prominent littering in the Alief community, our efforts represented a small portion of a broader community effort that was inspired by community leaders such as environmental clubs at Alief Early College High School, Ms. Barbara Quattro, and Alan Steinberg, Chair of the Clean City Commission in Houston.

— THE OFFICE OF COUNCIL MEMBER TIFFANY D. THOMAS —

DISTRICT F COMMUNITY CLEAN-UP

Join District, CRR, AliefVotes, and Keep Houston Beautiful for a community clean-up in Alief.

Saturday, July 27th, 2024

9 AM to 11 AM

11679 Harwin Dr.

Volunteer:

832-393-3002 | DISTRICTF@HOUSTONTX.GOV | WWW.HOUSTONTX.GOV/COUNCIL/F/

@TIFFANYFORALIEF

ALIEF CLEAN-UP

Join AliefVotes and the Alief Super Neighborhood Council for a youth-led community clean-up! Everyone is invited.

SATURDAY, AUGUST 30, 2025

12 PM TO 1 PM

8150 HOWELL SUGARLAND RD, HOUSTON, TX 77083
BEECHNUT ST NEAR KERR HIGH SCHOOL

RSVP NOW at bit.ly/Beechnutcleanup

Figure 31. Example flyers for community clean-ups that were led by AliefVotes students and associated partners. From location selection and outreach to final execution, these events played a small part in ensuring we are resilient.

ALIEF COMMUNITY TREE PLANTINGS

Embedded in the legacy of the Alief Super Neighborhood Council under the leadership of the late chair, Ms. Barbara Quattro, are over 10,000 trees planted in the Alief community since the early 2000s. Each tree planting results in 100-150 saplings planted, thanks to the generous donation from Trees for Houston. Many organizations involved include SEWA International Incorporated, District F, Houston Tree Initiative, Trees for Houston, Texas A&M Forestry Service, Alief ISD, and Bank of America. AliefVotes has secured over \$390,000 in tree-planting grants for the Alief area, while also leading plantings at Taylor High School and O'Donnell Middle School sidewalks. These tree plantings, over the past two decades, have been historic in bringing the community together through dedicated volunteerism, where we mitigate the issue of an urban heat island and the fact that Alief is 10-15 degrees hotter than other areas of Houston, one tree at a time.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

ASNC
ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

sewa

INVITES YOU TO VOLUNTEER AT OUR
TREE PLANTING
on
SATURDAY, OCTOBER 25, 2025
8:45 AM – 10:30 AM

LOCATION TBD: SOUTH DAIRY ASHFORD BETWEEN BISSONNET AND WEST BELFORT.

IN MEMORY OF BARBARA QUATTRO. LET'S CELEBRATE HER LEADERSHIP BY DOING GOOD WORK.

FOR FURTHER DETAILS: aliefsuperneighborhood@gmail.com

Note: This is a save-the-date flyer—more information about the exact address and Celebration of Life Memorial to come.

ASNC
ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

Let's PLANT TREES

ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL AND TREE INITIATIVE

Join us to help increase tree coverage in Alief!

11.22.2025
From 8 AM to 12 PM

Location: 12200 S Dairy Ashford Rd
Houston, TX 77099

Signup

CLICK HERE TO SIGN UP!
link: <https://tinyurl.com/aliefplanting>

ASNC
ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

Scotts

INVITES YOU TO VOLUNTEER AT OUR
TREE PLANTING
& community celebration on
SATURDAY, APRIL 26, 2025
9AM – 12PM

PARKING: 9200 WILCREST DR, HOUSTON, TX 77099

ALIEF IS CURRENTLY AN URBAN HEAT ISLAND HELP US MAINTAIN TREES!

FOR FURTHER DETAILS: bquattro@sbcglobal.net

BANK OF AMERICA

GENEROUS SPONSOR OF THE ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL TREE PLANTING PROGRAM

Arbor Day Foundation

ASNC
ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

INVITES YOU TO VOLUNTEER AT OUR
TREE PLANTING
on
SATURDAY, MARCH 22, 2025
9AM – 12PM

PARKING: 9400 WILCREST DR. HOUSTON, TX 77099

ALIEF IS CURRENTLY AN URBAN HEAT ISLAND HELP US PLANT TREES!

Figure 32. A small sample of student-created flyers over recent years for community-led tree plantings, often led by the Alief Super Neighborhood Council. The largest funders included the Arbor Day Foundation, Bank of America, and more.

Figure 33. A GIS Google Map of tree plantings (last updated 2024) of plantings in the Alief area. Our goal is to ensure that every single media that does not have a tree is filled in the coming years.

According to Houston Public Media and the Houston Advanced Research Center, heat directly affects a community's resilience. Alief experiences the urban heat island effect, where some areas of Houston are 10-14 degrees hotter than others due to low tree canopy coverage (11%) and the prevalence of concrete and asphalt. This occurs because cities have more heat-absorbing surfaces, such as asphalt and buildings, that generate heat from activities like traffic and industry, and lack sufficient vegetation to provide cooling through shade and evaporation. Urban Heat Islands (UHIs) can increase energy demand for cooling, harm air and water quality, and lead to adverse health impacts. UHIs and their challenges have prompted investments, including \$250,000 from the Arbor Day Foundation after the passage of the Inflation Reduction Act, \$500,000 from the Environmental Protection Agency in partnership with SEWA International, and \$2 million from the Alief Linear Forest Project by Harris County Precinct 4.

TREE PLANTING EDUCATION & GENERATIONAL LEGACY

ALIEFVOTES & THE RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK

TREE PLANTING COMMUNITY WORKSHOP

Everyone is invited. Over free lunch and drinks, learn about tree-planting initiatives in Alief and how to get involved. Volunteer: Tree planting starts at 9 AM at 9400 Wilcrest Dr.

Saturday, March 22, 2025

12:30 PM to 2 PM

Hear from Special Guest: Ms. Barbara Quattro

LOCATION: Alief Neighborhood Center
11903 Bellaire Blvd. Houston, TX 77072 (Room 2003)

Register NOW!
Free Food, Brochures, & More!
bit.ly/alief-tree-workshop

832-209-6616 | ALIEFVOTES@GMAIL.COM | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG
@ALIEFVOTES

Figure 34. Tree Planting Community Workshop at the Alief Neighborhood Center in partnership with Harris County Precinct 4, District F, the Alief Super Neighborhood Council, Mi Familia Vota, and the National Wildlife Federation.

Tree planting and community organizing are not limited to one generation only. We must engage youth and the next generation to pass on the torch. One example, funded by the Resilient Cities Network, was our tree-planting workshop, attended by over 50 community members and led by students. We also want to thank Alice Lee for her donation to support this workshop, as well as all the speakers, such as Barbara Quattro and Precinct 4.

TRANSIT WORKSHOPS

Connecting Communities Transit Workshop

ALIEF VOTES LINK HOUSTON

Join us to discuss public transportation in Alief and participate in an exciting Art & Transit activity!

Lunch will be provided.

**SATURDAY
AUG 10TH
10:30 - 2:00 PM**

Chinese Community Center
9800 Town Park Dr.,
Houston, TX, 77036

REGISTER BY AUGUST 8TH:
bit.ly/alief1

ALIEFVOTES & LINK HOUSTON PRESENTS

Transit Workshop

In this workshop, you will gain a deeper understanding of transit issues in Alief, participate in an interactive listening session, and learn about resilience efforts in transportation.

**Saturday, June 28, 2025
11 AM to 1 PM**

Alief Community Center
11903 Bellaire Blvd, Houston, TX 77072 (Room 1509)

Register Now!
Free lunch, networking opportunities, & More!

tinyurl.com/alief-transit-2025

ALIEF VOTES LINK HOUSTON RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK

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@ALIEFVOTES

Figure 35. Transit Workshop hosted by students at the Alief Neighborhood Center and the Chinese Community Center across 2024 and 2025, led by students and partners such as LINK Houston, who focus on transportation advocacy.

Central to resilience is also access to public transportation. Whether it's the #2 line on Bellaire, the need for an Alief METRO Circulator, or a lack of coverage at bus stops, we heard and listened to residents, which allowed us to relay their concerns to the city and local officials. We'd especially like to thank LINK Houston and Ms. Cherrelle Duncan for their steadfast collaboration and advocacy in the Alief area.

Figure 35b. Alief Neighborhood Center Transit Workshop, led by LINK Houston Leaders and AliefVotes students. Through an intimate discussion and roundtable format, we learned much about the needs of the community.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

HURRICANE BERYL FOOD & WATER DISTRIBUTION

Figure 36. Led by the Office of Council Member Tiffany D. Thomas, AliefVotes participated with community partners and the Food Bank on the distribution efforts in the aftermath of Hurricane Beryl through three food and water distributions.

A significant reason for the creation of this report was the devastating aftermath of Hurricane Beryl and the straight-line Derecho during the Summer of 2024. This hurricane, alongside vivid memories of Hurricane Harvey, the Tax Day Floods, the Memorial Day Floods, and more, prompted a renewed commitment to ensuring that Alief community members are safe, educated, and have opportunities to recover. The Office of Houston City Council Member Tiffany D. Thomas, District F, led such efforts. Council Member Thomas has represented the Alief area since 2019 alongside other vital communities on the West Side (“the Best Side”, as she often declares!). A large number of cars and volunteers at these distributions represents demand across all neighborhoods in the Alief community.

Figure 36b. Snapshots from senior delivery initiatives, water distributions that Walmart sponsored, and Alan Steinberg directing traffic at Crump Stadium.

GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE WITH POCKET PRAIRIES

What better way to involve a community than to execute a project that the Alief neighbors decide on? Our two-pocket prairie projects represented exactly that. Through collaboration and funding from the Resilient Cities Network, the National Wildlife Federation, and the Harris County Climate Justice Plan, AliefVotes led the implementation of two local pocket prairies (green infrastructure) at the Alief Community Garden and Brays Village East HOA. Through four intense community meetings, residents voted among several projects that included additional tree plantings, bioswales, rain gardens, and pocket prairies. With a tight tie, pocket prairies won at just above 51% of the votes.

~ RESILIENT ALIEF ~
COMMUNITY MEETING: 02.06.25

Help us select a climate resilience project for the neighborhood. *Be a voice for your community!*

Let us know you're coming! Scan the QR code to register.
Date: Thursday, February 6, 2025
Time: 6:30 - 7:30 pm
Location: Alief Community Center (11903 Bellaire Blvd, Houston, TX 77072) Room 1511/1512 (Past the Gym)
bit.ly/nwf-alief-2

Free box dinner provided as a take-home after the event!
 Questions? Email ungerk@nwf.org or aliefvotes@gmail.com

ALIEFVOTES & PARTNERS PRESENT

ALIEF POCKET PRAIRIE
PLANTING VOLUNTEER DAY

Join Alief ISD student leaders, Mr. Kyle Frese (Founder of Decentralized Farming LLC), Ms. Kate Unger with the National Wildlife Federation, and the Resilient Cities Network, to plant at the **second pocket prairie** at Brays Village East in Alief.

SATURDAY, OCTOBER 4, 2025
10 AM TO ~12 PM

LOCATION: Brays Village East HOA in Alief
 10615 High Star Drive Houston, Texas 77072

SIGN UP NOW!
 Learn from Growing Green Thumbs and Alabama Community Gardens to learn about growing your own food, food forests, and propagation.

Register: tinyurl.com/pocket-prairie-alief
 Sign up using the QR code. Family Friendly!

ALIEF VOTES | RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK | NATIONAL WILDLIFE FEDERATION

Decentralized Farming LLC | **ASNC** | ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

832-209-6616 | ADMIN@ALIEFVOTES.ORG | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG
 @ALIEFVOTES

~ RESILIENT ALIEF ~
COMMUNITY MEETING: 03.18.25

Help us select a climate resilience project for the neighborhood. *Be a voice for your community!*

Let us know you're coming! Scan the QR code to register.
Date: Tuesday, March 18, 2025
Time: 6:30 - 7:30 pm
Location: Alief Community Center (11903 Bellaire Blvd, Houston, TX 77072) Room 1511/1512 (Past the Gym)
bit.ly/nwf-alief-3

Free box dinner provided as a take-home after the event!
 Questions? Email ungerk@nwf.org or aliefvotes@gmail.com

ALIEFVOTES & PARTNERS PRESENT

ALIEF POCKET PRAIRIE
PLANTING VOLUNTEER DAY

Join expert Mr. Kyle Frese (Founder of Decentralized Farming LLC), Ms. Kate Unger with the National Wildlife Federation, Urban Network, and the Resilient Cities Network, to plant at the pocket prairie at the Alief Community Garden!

SATURDAY, SEPTEMBER 27, 2025
10 AM TO ~12 PM

LOCATION: Alief Community Garden
 8409 1/2 Dairy View Ln, Houston, TX 77072 (Meet at the Pocket Prairie)

SIGN UP NOW!
 Learn from Growing Green Thumbs and Alabama Community Gardens to learn about growing your own food, food forests, and propagation.

Register: tinyurl.com/pocket-prairie-alief
 Sign up using the QR code. Family Friendly!

ALIEF VOTES | RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK | NATIONAL WILDLIFE FEDERATION

Decentralized Farming LLC | **ASNC** | ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

832-209-6616 | ADMIN@ALIEFVOTES.ORG | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG
 @ALIEFVOTES

ALIEFVOTES & PARTNERS PRESENT

ALIEF POCKET PRAIRIE
COMMUNITY BUILD DAY

AliefVotes, the Resilient Cities Network, and the National Wildlife Federation are building a pocket prairie at the Alief Community Garden. Come ready to help us! Wear long pants and prepare to get your hands dirty.

SATURDAY, JUNE 21, 2025
10 AM TO 12 PM

LOCATION: Alief Community Garden
 8409 1/2 Dairy View Ln, Houston, TX 77072

SIGN UP NOW!
 We will also learn how pocket prairies improve water quality, reduce pollution, and support local wildlife—then help build one yourself on Friday!

Register: tinyurl.com/pocket-prairie-alief
 Sign up using the QR code. Family Friendly!

ALIEF VOTES | RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK | NATIONAL WILDLIFE FEDERATION

Decentralized Farming LLC | **ASNC** | ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

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ALIEFVOTES & PARTNERS PRESENT

ALIEF POCKET PRAIRIE
SEEDING, WORKSHOP, & TOUR

AliefVotes, the Resilient Cities Network, and the National Wildlife Federation are building a pocket prairie at the Alief Community Garden. Come ready to help us seed and learn about the importance of green infrastructure.

SATURDAY, JULY 19, 2025
10 AM TO ~12 PM

LOCATION: Alief Community Garden
 8409 1/2 Dairy View Ln, Houston, TX 77072

SIGN UP NOW!
 We will also learn how pocket prairies improve water quality, reduce pollution, and support local wildlife. Additionally, there will be a garden tour.

Register: tinyurl.com/pocket-prairie-alief
 Sign up using the QR code. Family Friendly!

ALIEF VOTES | RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK | NATIONAL WILDLIFE FEDERATION

Decentralized Farming LLC | **ASNC** | ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

832-209-6616 | ALIEFVOTES@GMAIL.COM | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG
 @ALIEFVOTES

National Wildlife Federation Community Meeting!

A group photo of diverse community members smiling and posing for a group picture at a community meeting. The photo is framed with a decorative border.

Figure 37. Various events from the pocket prairie project, ranging from volunteer days, community building days, environmental education workshops, and resilient cities feedback workshops.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

The story truly begins in early 2024 at the Alief Community Garden, seven acres at the corner of Beechnut and Dairy View that ABC13 news called a little United Nations. Here, Vietnamese gardeners tend rows of Thai basil, purple perilla, and lemongrass. Burmese families cultivate bottle gourds in wooden trellises for traditional soups. Nigerian growers nurture pepper varieties that connect them to ancestral lands. Pakistani gardeners coax onions and winter melons for curry. Congolese women tend cabbage and sweet potatoes.

Through four meticulously planned, student-led community meetings at the Alief Neighborhood Center in late 2024 and early 2025, youth leaders, in collaboration with the Resilient Cities Network and the National Wildlife Federation, facilitated conversations that honored Alief's magnificent diversity. Student leaders Ninet Flores Miranda and Mia Nguyen stood before their neighbors on February 6, 2025, presenting climate resilience options in accessible language, with interpretation services ensuring every voice could be heard.

Figure 38. Second Pocket Prairie Build Day at the Alief Neighborhood Center, which included the installation of the sign, soil addition, bench addition, and more.

The crescendo came on September 27, 2025. Over 50 volunteers, representing the full, beautiful spectrum of Alief's diversity, gathered for the major planting day. Kyle Frese from Decentralized Farming LLC led workshops on growing food sustainably. Kate Unger shared National Wildlife Federation expertise about prairie ecosystems. Urban Harvest, Growing Green Thumbs, and Alabama Community Gardens brought decades of combined knowledge about native plants and community gardening.

And then they planted. 240 native Texas plants went into the ground that day: Gulf Coast Muhly grasses that would sway silver in the breeze, Texas Coneflowers in bold yellows, Aquatic Milkweed to host monarch butterflies on their epic migrations, Indian Blanket wildflowers in brilliant oranges and reds that would carpet the prairie each spring, Seaside Goldenrod, Gulf Coast Penstemon, Lyreleaf Sage. Each species was chosen not just for beauty but for ecological function.

Figure 39. Various photos from the third and first pocket prairie plant days at the Alief Community Garden, with native planting led by Mr. Kyle Frese of Decentralized Farming LLC and Ms. Kate Unger and Ms. Mayra Fowler from National Wildlife Federation.

Perhaps the most remarkable chapter of community-driven innovation began in June 2025 at a Brays Village East Homeowners Association meeting. Board Chair Alfonso Peña and Board Member Paul Dunnand were discussing a persistent problem with their HOA members: maintenance crews kept mowing through a neglected area near the clubhouse, causing erosion, wasting resources, and creating an eyesore. The community had tried various solutions, but nothing stuck.

When the Resilient Cities Network heard about this organic community opportunity, they responded with the flexibility that defined their partnership approach. By October 4, 2025, when the second prairie at Brays Village East held its build day, the community ownership was evident in every detail. They were signing their names on the archway, literally inscribing themselves into their neighborhood's infrastructure. Families who had initially been skeptical about losing lawn space were now the prairie's most prominent champions, explaining to new neighbors how the native plants would reduce their HOA's maintenance costs while preventing erosion. The prairie wasn't something done for them or to them. It was something they built together, with youth leadership showing them what was possible and the community making it their own.

Figure 40. Second Pocket Prairie Build Day in October of 2025 and National Recognition of our Work through the Resilient Cities Network Convening in Chicago, Illinois.

STUDENT SNAPSHOTS: POCKET PRAIRIES

We are excited to report that both pocket prairies are complete! Below are high-resolution photos taken by Alief ISD student Cailey Andal.

Figure 41. Student-taken shots of the first and second pocket prairie at the Alief Community Garden and Brays Village East HOA.

BUILDING MOMENTUM THROUGH MEDIA

Extreme heat exposure puts people at risk of fatigue, dehydration, respiratory difficulties, exhaustion, and heat stroke.

Figure 42. Shots from the Resilient Cities Network Filming Clips and Various Interviews and B-Rolls.

Building media momentum is incredibly important for Alief. Whether it's news coverage or filming with the Resilient Cities Network, highlighting the issues in Alief such as extreme heat exposure, real lived experiences, and the shared reality in an incredibly diverse and vital way is powerful in building consensus through education. Whether it's Ny'Elle Blount, our AliefVotes Director of Data & Records, or Alexandra Onwuli, AliefVotes Director of Communication, we ensured that youth leadership was first and foremost when it came to highlighting that our community is strong, resilient, and effective when it comes to finding strategies for hazard mitigation.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT THROUGH ROUNDTABLES

Figure 43. Various flyers from the three community engagement workshops and roundtables organized by AliefVotes.

AliefVotes, perhaps most importantly, organized three disaster preparedness roundtables and workshops with youth leadership at the forefront. The first workshop was at the Chinese Community Center (new location due to the number of registrants) on November 9, 2024, a workshop in collaboration with Woori Juntos on April 17, 2025, and a disaster preparedness roundtable on September 13, 2025, at the Alief Neighborhood Center. Each of these workshops focused on listening to community members on their concerns in the neighborhood through keynote speakers, breakout sections, and community roundtable sessions facilitated by our Alief ISD student leaders.

Figure 43b. Student-taken shots of community members and stakeholders participating in the disaster preparedness roundtable.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

Figure 44. Pictured is Congresswoman Lizzie Fletcher’s Office and HOPE Clinic Tabling with Community Members.

Figure 45. Student leaders and organizers are posing with civic engagement workshop flyers and guest speaker Leah.

Figure 46. Group picture with all stakeholders and community roundtable participants at the Alief Neighborhood Center.

Learn more at aliefvotes.org/disaster | For the youth, by the youth.

Figure 47. Photo from September 2024 Workshop at the Chinese Community Center, with 100 Disaster Preparedness Kits Distributed to the community for all ages and all neighborhoods.

Figure 48. Additional photos with stakeholders, kits, and student leadership during the disaster preparedness workshops.

DISASTER PREPAREDNESS FINDINGS

Figure 49. Speaking is Reverend Dr. Mark Brown, the Chief Executive Officer of the West Houston Assistance Ministries

On September 13, 2025, AliefVotes and partners hosted a comprehensive policy and community feedback-focused roundtable in Room 1511/12 at the Alief Neighborhood Center from 11 AM to 2 PM. Approximately 40 total participants included students from all Alief ISD high schools (Kerr, Taylor, Elsie, Hastings, and Alief Early), long-term residents, representatives from community organizations, government liaisons, and immigrant community advocates, reflecting the area's demographic diversity.

One of the cited devastating experiences, Winter Storm Uri, emerged as the most traumatic disaster for participants. Dianne Purvis described being **"8 days without water, phone, TV, no electric, no refrigerator"** and having to use water from **"a little man-made pond to flush the bathroom"** with "no one came out to help." Tom Temple, with decades of Houston disaster experience, called Uri **"the most frightening. Couldn't get out of town... They thought they were going to die"** with **"the whole house filled with smoke and went down to 40 degrees."**

There were also citations of power outage disparities: Hurricane Beryl created severe disparities in power restoration. One participant was **"out of power for 14 days" during the Derecho, while "Beryl was 2 days,"** highlighting inconsistent utility prioritization. Jabria, a young driver, experienced dangerous conditions, including **"hydroplaning heading home from school, and pulled over during the storm."**

Economically, residents revealed a hidden consequence of repeated disasters: "People of modest income have lost their homes because they could not afford the insurance premiums. It went from \$2,000 a year to over \$5,000. There have been people forced out of their homes by the insurance rates." This 150% increase in three years represents disaster-induced gentrification affecting long-term residents. Community surveys showed "30 to 40% of Houstonians said they were thinking of leaving because so many people were left without power."

Many residents also had significant concerns about communication systems. One senior resident identified the fundamental flaw: **"One major problem is going to the internet. There is no electricity, and I can't get online. Phone went down. People can't look at that without electricity."** Neighbors echoed her remarks and emphasized the post-disaster void: **"Communication is zero, and you don't care how much they say. When you have no resources."** On top of these concerns, the lack of language diversity means many residents cannot access the most up-to-date information about disasters and post-disaster recovery.

Participants also expressed frustration with the lack of transparency in utility prioritization. "Everyone says we are helping, but there is a limitation of knowing when you are getting helped and when your house is going to get electricity. How do you prioritize neighborhoods? How does the chain of command work?" The CenterPoint website proved unreliable: **"During Beryl, CenterPoint did respond if you are on their email list... For some people, it updated, and for others, it did not."** This uncertainty underscores the importance of communication and having information in the community, which can significantly relieve anxieties and pressures. However, some residents pushed back, saying that CenterPoint could not give accurate timestamps because the nature of disaster recovery is variable and more frustrations will arise if "deadlines" are not met if they were set.

One non-profit leader from BRIDGE infrastructure, Koco, noted emergency communications cover **"only two languages primarily,"** excluding significant portions of Houston's diverse population. Azeb Yusuf from the City of Houston's New Americans office emphasized "language accessibility when it comes to ensuring that refugee and immigrant communities can access critical information. Current technology solutions like "QR Codes" may not be accessible to all community members." She also, drawing from healthcare administration experience, identified critical medical access failures: "They do not have a mobile unit... Access to prescription medications. It is hard for clients to get their medication." Specific needs included: "With people with Asthma and Oxygen, it was tough for them to get their information. There was no mobile EKG, ultrasound, etc." The absence of mobile medical units particularly affected refugee and immigrant communities, who lacked established healthcare relationships or transportation.

Ishy, a local cyclist and Alief student, noted dangerous conditions: **"Dairy Ashford and Richmond at night or in the rain is horrible, and a road gets really bad, especially one that is as used as Richmond."** Poor road conditions affect both daily safety and emergency vehicle access. Dianne asked about "antiquated poles and it cost much money", while participants noted "Beryl knocked down the tree and the connection," showing how single failures cascade through neighborhoods. Linda Mueller raised concerns about bayou maintenance: "Bayous are supposed to be cleaned, but it's half full right now."

Despite challenges, strong community networks emerged as assets. Sarai Robinson noted "Council Member Thomas knows her community very well and by name" and "Alief constituents are very active... HOAs are meeting, civic meetings, PIP meetings." Jen from Congresswoman Fletcher's office observed that **"environmental disasters are a special kind of moment in which people do unite and trust each other."** Randall praised phone-based alerts during the Derecho: "Having dinner with his kids and got a phone alert to take shelter now... that system does work." He emphasized that "the cell phones do work" as a reliable emergency communication method. Traditional communication proved most reliable. Cindy noted, **"Word of mouth is the best one yet"** for emergency communication. Jabria described how "during Beryl and Harvey... they have Nextdoor. When electricity came back on, they were looking for pets and family members."

Figure 50. Alief community of all residents speaking and discussing while the AliefVotes team transcribed and analyzed comments.

Tom Temple highlighted humanitarian efforts during the freeze, noting that "they were checking on a lot of homeless people on Bissonnet and Kirkwood and HPD was there. They did a heck of a job showing some humanitarian" response. This demonstrated how community members and first responders worked together to check on vulnerable populations during extreme weather. Kyle, who **"didn't grow up with Bayous," gained appreciation for Houston's natural drainage systems, observing how "the streets are filling up and it showed him how the bayou works and how well they can work with the drainage."** Bretta confirmed that Houston's bayous "were man made," highlighting how engineered natural infrastructure can be effective when properly maintained.

Participants suggested better **"collaboration with restaurants"** for food distribution and more systematic pre-planning for emergency resource distribution. The current approach seemed reactive rather than proactive, with limited advance planning for how to efficiently distribute food, water, and other necessities during extended emergencies. Bretta suggested "radio and cracking it. Those things need to be available through maybe a grant. Maybe you need an AM radio. The crank of radio can be very helpful and they are real big. **In the Latino community radio is a huge form of communication when there is no power."**

EDUCATION MATTERS

In addition to the roundtable portion, AliefVotes had a serious intent to educate the community about the functions of certain entities. At the September 13, 2025, Disaster Preparedness Workshop, Alief community members heard from an array of governmental and nonprofit leaders who play key roles in local emergency planning. Speakers included WHAM CEO Rev. Dr. Mark Brown, who highlighted the importance of nonprofit involvement in disaster recovery; Harris County Precinct 4 Senior Director Walter Hambrick, who discussed infrastructure, preparedness kits, and community education; and City of Houston Office of Emergency Management Chief Public Information Officer Ruth Tovar, who shared essential hurricane preparedness information and citywide response resources. Community members also heard from Harris County Public Health Community Resilience Manager Halley Maxwell, who explained the county's public health response strategy, and CenterPoint Energy Director of Emergency Response Operations Thomas Jacobus, who guided power outage preparation and energy safety. Additional representatives from the offices of Council Members Tiffany Thomas, Julian Ramirez, and Sallie Alcorn were in attendance, and organizations such as Congresswoman Lizzie Fletcher's Office, Alief ISD FACE, HOPE Clinic, and the City of Houston Housing & Community Development Department participated through tabling and engagement.

Figure 51. Community roundtable photo during the September 2025 workshop with the Resilient Cities Network.

At the November 9, 2024. Environmental Justice & Hurricane Preparedness Workshop, attendees learned from a diverse coalition of environmental, civic, and community organizations. Keynote speaker Jennifer Hadayia, Executive Director of Air Alliance Houston, addressed environmental justice, air quality, and opportunities for student involvement. Additional speakers included Mi Familia en Acción organizer Jossue Ureño on hurricane preparation and community organizing; Trees for Houston Executive Director Barry Ward on heat mitigation and urban tree canopy expansion; SEWA International’s disaster-preparedness team on volunteerism and recovery efforts; and National Wildlife Federation representative Kate Unger on youth-led conservation. Leaders from the City of Houston and Harris County—including Chief of Staff Isaac Eguia from District F and Senior Analyst Julia Ossemi-Seied from Harris County Flood Control—shared updates on city and county resilience efforts. Keep Houston Beautiful and the Alief Super Neighborhood Council, represented by Dr. Alan Steinberg, also contributed insights on infrastructure and community improvement. Together, these partners equipped Alief families with the knowledge, tools, and multilingual resources needed to better prepare for future disasters.

Finally, power outages were one of the most widespread and urgent concerns in Alief, with residents from Huntington Village to neighborhoods around Hackberry Park reporting prolonged outages, spoiled food, and limited access to ice and water. On Tuesday night, after a storm, a man with ALS reached out seeking help because his backup system had failed after being without power since early Monday. It took nearly two hours to reach 911, and by the time emergency responders arrived, his son had connected a car battery to an inverter to help him breathe. Cooling centers in Alief also opened too late. The Alief Neighborhood Center did not open immediately after the storm, and although the City has approved funding for a generator, installation will take several fiscal years.

Downed trees blocked major roadways, and while the City partnered with the Department of Neighborhoods, Heads Up Houston, and Career and Recovery Services to clear debris, more investment is needed to keep roads passable and intersections—such as S. Kirkwood and Bellaire—adequately powered. Language access was another significant barrier. For residents who rely on METRO or are trying to conserve gas during blocked-road conditions, traveling long distances to basic relief sites is not feasible.

FURTHER COMMUNITY WORKSHOPS & CIVIC WORK

THE OFFICE OF COUNCIL MEMBER TIFFANY D. THOMAS
Are you a small business owner affected by Hurricane Beryl?

SMALL BUSINESS WORKSHOP

In the aftermath of the Hurricane, Join District F and the Small Business Administration to learn more about recovery, financial assistance, and disaster loans.

Monday, July 29th, 2024
6:30 PM to 7:30 PM

The Church Without Walls - Eldridge
 7500 Eldridge Pkwy, Houston, TX 77083

832-393-3002 | DISTRICTF@HOUSTONTX.GOV | WWW.HOUSTONTX.GOV/COUNCIL/F/

@TIFFANYFORALIEF

ALIEFVOTES, MI FAMILIA EN ACCIÓN, & HARC:

HEAT RESILIENCE COMMUNITY WORKSHOP

Everyone is invited. Over free lunch and drinks, learn about heat resilience and food justice initiatives in Alief and how to get involved!

Saturday, April 5, 2025
11:30 AM to 1 PM

Tracy Gee Community Center
 3599 Westcenter Dr, Houston, TX 77042

Register NOW!
 Free Food, Brochures, & More!
tinyurl.com/heat-workshop-alief

832-209-6616 | ALIEFVOTES@GMAIL.COM | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG

@ALIEFVOTES

ALIEFVOTES PRESENTS

Small Business Expo

Open to all families, entrepreneurs, students, and community! Join us to support local businesses, network with others in the community, and learn about available resources and opportunities.

Saturday, April 19, 2025
4 PM to 6 PM

Salvation Army in Alief
 7920 Cook Rd, Houston, TX 77072

Register Now!
 Free dinner, networking opportunities, & More!

Organized by Edgar & Cailey, AliefVotes Fellows
 Register: bit.ly/alief-business-expo

832-209-6616 | ALIEFVOTES@GMAIL.COM | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG

@ALIEFVOTES

ALIEFVOTES & HEB PRESENTS

HEALTHCARE FAIR

Open to all families! Free health screenings are available. Explore local businesses supporting Alief's well-being and discuss healthcare benefits and health issues with professionals while getting tested.

Saturday, April 12, 2025
3 PM to 6 PM

Hear from Guests: Dr. Thalia Micah, Precinct 4, & More!

Alief Kerr High School
 8150 Howell Sugarland Rd, Houston, TX 77083

Register Now!
 Free Snacks, Screenings, & More!
bit.ly/alief-health-fair

Volunteers, please fill out the form.

832-209-6616 | ALIEFVOTES@GMAIL.COM | WWW.ALIEFVOTES.ORG

@ALIEFVOTES

Figure 52. Photos from additional resilience workshops that included a small business workshop, a heat resilience workshop at the Tracy Gee Community Center, a small business expo to strengthen community ties, and a healthcare fair with HEB.

THE OFFICE OF COUNCIL MEMBER TIFFANY D. THOMAS

FIRE SAFETY CANVASS

It's time to take action! Volunteer with the District F office to canvass the Alief neighborhood of Catalina Square after the recent June fire. Help spread awareness on best practices for keeping loved ones safe. Everyone is welcome to join!

TUESDAY, JULY 15, 2025
10 AM TO 12 PM

LOCATION: Catalina Square Neighborhood
 Meet at 11920 Beechnut St, Houston, TX 77072

VOLUNTEER NOW
 Join us to spread the word on how to protect your home and loved ones after the recent June fire in Catalina Square in District F.

Register here: tinyurl.com/fire-canvass-alief

THE OFFICE OF COUNCIL MEMBER TIFFANY D. THOMAS, DISTRICT F

TIFFANY D. THOMAS

ALIEF SUPERNEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL PRESENTS

Join us on the fourth Tuesday of every month for an Alief community meeting. Hear updates from elected officials, the police department, community events, and connect with neighbors and friends.

ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL MONTHLY MEETING

TUESDAY, AUGUST 26, 2025
6:30 PM to 8 PM

Alief Neighborhood Center
 11903 Bellaire Blvd, Houston, TX 77072, Room 1D 1512
 (Walk towards the back, past the gym)

ALIEF SUPER NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

Follow us on Facebook and Instagram:
 (@aliefsuperneighborhood)

Sign up for regular updates from the ASNC Team:
aliefsuperneighborhood.org/mailling-list-archives/

HOUSTON CLIMATE MOVEMENT & PARTNERS PRESENT:

2025 HOUSTON COMMUNITY CLIMATE SUMMIT

The climate crisis is already here in Houston. Whether you're a longtime climate advocate or just beginning your journey, this summit is designed for you.

SATURDAY, SEPTEMBER 27, 2025
9 AM TO 3 PM

Shrine of The Black Madonna Cultural and Event Center
 5309 Martin Luther King Blvd Houston, TX 77021

Free & open to all – youth, families, elders, organizers, Join us for a theme of youth empowerment. newcomers, artists, educators, and more. Attendees must register.

REGISTER NOW
 Register here:
tinyurl.com/houston-climate-summit

ORGANIZED BY THE HOUSTON CLIMATE MOVEMENT. GET INVOLVED!

Additional events organized by AliefVotes included heat, business expos, healthcare fairs, small-business workshops, and more. Indeed, resilience touches many topics and thus requires an intersection with subjects that touch the welfare of all community members in the Alief area and beyond.

Figure 53. Additional initiatives for resilience included a fire safety canvass, monthly Alief Super Neighborhood Council Meetings, and partner events such as the 2025 Houston Community Climate Summit.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

At the heart of change is policy. AliefVotes is a non-partisan 501(c)(3) and thus does not endorse any political party, nor candidate, nor specific policy recommendations. The following ideas and proposals have been collected through various community members, roundtable sessions, discussions with elected officials, and more. These suggestions are further revised and reviewed by stakeholders through our intensive editing process. The following pages present policy suggestions spanning various levels of government, including the federal Congress, the Texas Legislature (in preparation for the 90th session in 2027), and local policies related to the City of Houston under a predominantly strong-mayor executive. As always, we welcome open conversation and prudent debate on these recommendations, as they serve as starting points for the long, iterative legislative process that often extends across all areas of governance. A principal focus that arises out of this report is geared towards the 90th Session of the Texas Legislature, given the hastier and accelerated nature for proposals.

Figure 54. A view of the Texas House of Representatives in the Austin-based Capitol, in which 150 legislators across the State of Texas convene in odd-numbered years from January to June.

CONGRESSIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

Congress could codify direct-to-city allocation for all future United States Housing and Urban Development (HUD) disaster recovery and infrastructure funds, particularly for Texas jurisdictions with populations exceeding 50,000 residents. Following Hurricane Harvey, HUD delegated over \$5.6 billion in CDBG-DR funding to the Texas General Land Office rather than allocating it directly to impacted cities, resulting in significant delays, discrimination in the distribution of funds, and administrative bottlenecks that left thousands of storm survivors waiting up to 6 years for home repairs and buyouts. This is particularly impactful for Alief residents across multiple subdivisions.

Despite being the most impacted urban center, Houston and Harris County received little to no funding from the first \$1 billion in CDBG-MIT funds. HUD later determined that GLO's allocation formula had a discriminatory effect on Black and Latino-majority neighborhoods. In contrast, the American Rescue Plan Act of 2021 allocated \$607.8 million directly to Houston under the State and Local Fiscal Recovery Fund, enabling the city to deploy resources far more quickly and tailor programs through local control and city-based expertise.

Accordingly, Congress could prevent state preemption or gatekeeping of federal funds to cities, particularly in states with poor distribution records, and require that federal housing and disaster resources be distributed based on population needs, economic vulnerability, and disaster exposure rather than political considerations. The U.S. Senate Committee on Banking, Housing, and Urban Affairs is uniquely and especially positioned to advance legislation to institutionalize direct allocation and oversight structures, building on the bipartisan momentum through the Renewing Opportunity in the American Dream to Housing Act of 2025.

Note: Direct-to-city allocation is not a new proposal. Local governments, housing advocates, and Members of Congress have long argued that routing disaster funds through state agencies, particularly in states with documented distribution challenges. Despite these efforts, the Texas General Land Office continues to control HUD disaster recovery and mitigation funds, and proposals to change this structure have not advanced.

CONGRESSIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

Additionally, Congress could permanently extend FEMA temporary housing assistance from 18 months to 28 months for all presidentially declared disasters. Disaster recovery timelines have lengthened significantly due to supply chain disruptions, contractor shortages, and increased disaster frequency, requiring extended rebuilding periods. The current 18-month timeframe fails to account for the complex recovery processes disaster survivors must navigate, including protracted insurance claims, permitting delays, and construction challenges. Extending temporary housing assistance would provide critical stability for families facing housing insecurity during recovery, reducing the risk of homelessness and displacement that compounds the long-term economic and social impacts of disasters on affected communities.

Figure 55. A view of the United States House of Representatives in the Washington D.C.-based Capitol, in which 435 legislators across the nation convene in prudent debate and passage of federal legislation.

THE TEXAS LEGISLATURE: PROPOSALS

The following policy proposals are heavily focused and geared towards the 90th Legislature, in which offices will convene in Austin, Texas, in January 2027 to Sine Die in the same year. AliefVotes intends to hold productive, educational meetings with local state representatives and senators in the Houston area to ensure that these ideas remain starting points for potential legislative changes and the codification of community-rooted laws in the Texas statutes. If you are a local office, please do reach out to AliefVotes to continue these critical conversations at admin@aliefvotes.org.

CODIFYING TOLL BRIDGE FEES SUSPENSION DURING DECLARED DISASTERS

Based on community feedback during our December 6, 2025 roundtable, Alief residents have faced barriers in evacuation during extreme weather events. As a result, the Texas Legislature could amend Subchapter B, Chapter 372 of the Transportation Code in relation to Section 418.108 of the Texas Government Code (Title 4. Executive Branch, Subtitle B. Law Enforcement and Public Protection, Chapter 418. Emergency Management) to codify suspension of toll collections during an evacuation order during the declaration of local disasters.

Similar efforts have been implemented in Florida, where tolls on highways are often waived to enable faster evacuations. According to the State of Florida's Executive Office of the Governor, on October 7, 2024, Governor DeSantis suspended tolls across Central and West Florida for seven days in preparation for Hurricane Milton. The rationale was to ensure that residents can finalize and execute evacuation plans, whether mandated or not, without worrying about financial or logistical hurdles. Currently, Texas law and TxDOT policy allow toll entities to waive tolls in emergencies, including exemptions for emergency vehicles under Transportation Code §228.054, but Texas has no explicit, codified policy requiring automatic toll suspension across all toll authorities. Prior Republican support has been indicated in the Legislature through HB 2297 in the 89th Regular Legislative Session in Texas. Representatives Cunningham and Leo Wilson have previously supported this bill in the House Subcommittee on Transportation Funding. Based on the Legislative Budget Board analysis, no significant fiscal implication is anticipated.

FINANCIAL EXPLOITATION AND FINANCIAL ABUSE REMEDIES DURING DISASTERS

Residents have faced exploitation schemes during previous disasters and severe hurricanes, where residents and small businesses were disproportionately targeted due to disrupted infrastructure, language barriers, and evacuation stress. While existing law (including Chapter 100B, added by unanimous bipartisan passage of SB 2373 by Senator Nathan Johnson in the 89th Legislature) addresses certain AI-enabled financial exploitation, it does not apply a standardized multiplier for disaster-era deception, where heightened incidents occur.

The Texas Legislature could amend the Civil Practice & Remedies Code by adding Chapter 100C in Title 4 to include heightened liability for anyone who deploys or amplifies disaster-era scams using artificial intelligence, AI-enabled malicious messaging, synthetic media, or mass-automated phishing, with penalties scaling in severity beginning at Class A Misdemeanors for deceptive targeting in a declared disaster zone under Government Code §418.014 (governor disaster declaration) or §418.108 (local disaster declaration with evacuation authority).

While existing law allows for contractor and fraud penalties during disasters, it does not apply a standardized multiplier for AI-accelerated deception during declared disasters, nor does it guarantee confidentiality shielding for disaster claimants' personal data, benefits, or emergency distress calls within the Civil Practice and Remedies Code. Chapter 100C could also establish that any contractor who solicits disaster repair work using AI-generated credentials, including fabricated TDLR licenses, synthetic insurance certificates, or AI-manufactured testimonials, shall be liable for treble damages under the Deceptive Trade Practices Act (Business and Commerce Code Chapter 17). To protect vulnerable claimants, the chapter must also guarantee that personal data, benefit application records, and emergency distress calls of disaster fraud victims are shielded from public disclosure under the Texas Public Information Act (Government Code Chapter 552), and are not subject to discovery in civil litigation except by court order, ensuring those who report fraudulent schemes are not exposed to secondary victimization through data exploitation or retaliatory targeting.

CLARIFYING NON-PROFIT REGISTRATION FEE EXEMPTIONS FOR DISASTER RELIEF ORGANIZATIONS

Alief and other communities across Harris County have been subject to evacuation routes and severe impacts in the context of prior disasters, including Winter Storm Uri and Hurricane Beryl. The Texas Legislature could build on reforms enacted in 2023 ([HB 53, 88th Legislature](#)) and on earlier bipartisan proposals, such as [HB 1367 \(87th Legislature\)](#), which expanded [§502.454 of the Transportation Code \(Vehicles Used by Nonprofit Disaster Relief Organizations\)](#) to cover training, equipment maintenance, transportation of disaster relief supplies, and other disaster-related activities.

The Texas Legislature could further amend [Section 502.454\(a\)\(2\)](#) to explicitly include damage and needs assessment purposes, community preparedness education and outreach, vulnerable population identification and welfare check coordination, and search and rescue support as qualifying uses for registration fee exemptions. Additionally, the Legislature could add a new subsection to define "disaster relief supplies" to include direct relief goods such as food, water, medicine, and hygiene products, as well as administrative materials necessary for relief coordination, and fuel for vehicles and equipment used in disaster operations to ensure clarity in the transportation code.

Finally, the Legislature could amend [Section 502.454\(a\)\(1\)](#) to clarify that equipment trailers including those carrying generators, water purification systems, and mobile kitchens may be registered separately from tow vehicles, allowing organizations to deploy equipment flexibly across multiple response operations. Based on the existing \$5 registration fee structure and the limited universe of qualifying organizations, no significant fiscal implications to the state are anticipated. Perhaps a legislator may even find it prudent to amend the law to remove the \$5 registration fee if fiscal impact is insignificant.

EXPANDING NON-PROFIT REGISTRATION FEE EXEMPTIONS FOR DISASTER RELIEF ORGANIZATIONS

The Texas Legislature could build upon [HB 1367](#), filed during the 87th Legislative Session with bipartisan sponsorship, which amended Section 502.454 of the Transportation Code to expand vehicle registration fee exemptions for nonprofit disaster relief organizations from exclusive emergency use to include training, equipment maintenance, transportation of disaster relief supplies, and other activities related to disaster relief.

To further strengthen disaster response capacity and eliminate unnecessary administrative barriers, the Legislature could amend [Section 502.454 of the Transportation Code](#) to clarify that "nonprofit disaster relief organization" includes verified 501(c)(3) organizations, state-registered charitable organizations, or disaster response units formally recognized by a county, municipal, or state emergency management entity as an active disaster response partner. The Legislature could further amend [Section 502.454\(b\)](#) to streamline verification by requiring the Texas Department of Motor Vehicles to accept existing credentials such as FEMA volunteer registry status, Texas Voluntary Organizations Active in Disaster membership, American Red Cross disaster partner identification, or county emergency management designation in place of redundant documentation. Also, the Legislature could amend [Section 502.454\(b\)\(3\)](#) to require a description of the vehicle and any emergency equipment "if applicable," recognizing that not all relief vehicles are equipped with sirens, lights, or other emergency apparatus.

To improve operational efficiency for organizations with multiple vehicles, the Legislature could add a new subsection that permits nonprofit disaster relief organizations to submit a single consolidated fleet registration application for all qualifying cars, provided each vehicle is individually described. To reduce punitive friction for good-faith compliance from many non-profits, the Legislature could also add a provision clarifying that a car is not disqualified from exemption due to incidental or urgent use during a disaster period that is non-commercial, non-fraudulent, and directly in service of relief operations, provided a disaster response activity log is submitted to the Texas Department of Transportation within 30 days, and could modify [Section 502.454\(f\)](#) to permit compliance review using submitted disaster response activity logs rather than exclusive-use attestations alone. The anticipated fiscal note is minimal, but will have to be determined officially by the Texas Legislative Budget Board.

WAIVER FREEZE FOR POST-DISASTER BUILDING PERMIT FEES

Residents across Harris County and Alief have faced repeated disaster impacts, including Winter Storm Uri and Hurricane Beryl, during which those attempting to repair damaged homes encountered permitting costs that compounded financial strain during already difficult recovery periods. The Texas Legislature could amend Chapter 214 of the Local Government Code or Chapter 418 of the Government Code (depending on the Texas Legislative Council's recommendation) to establish an automatic building permit fee freeze for local governments located in areas designated in a governor-declared disaster under Section 418.014 or a FEMA-declared disaster. Under this bill, local governments in designated disaster areas would be prohibited from increasing building permit or inspection fees (permitting fee freeze) for 12 months (this timetable is subject to negotiation with stakeholders) following the disaster declaration, with an optional 6-month extension available by resolution of the governing body for areas demonstrating ongoing recovery needs.

Similar efforts have been achieved in Florida, where Section 553.80(8) of the Florida Statutes prohibited local governments in areas designated in FEMA disaster declarations for Hurricanes Ian and Nicole from raising building inspection fees following those storms. The rationale is to ensure that residents can initiate and complete necessary repairs to storm-damaged properties without facing increased regulatory costs during a period of constrained household budgets, insurance delays, and contractor shortages. Currently, Texas law explicitly authorizes municipalities to waive building permit fees in Neighborhood Empowerment Zones under Chapter 378. Outside those zones, cities must rely on general public-purpose authority and case law (such as *Barrington v. Cokinos*), and Texas has no disaster-triggered statutory fee freeze comparable to Florida's approach.

EXTENDING TENANT DISCLOSURE BEFORE LEASING IN HAZARDOUS ZONES

Tenants deserve to know whether their rented properties have been affected by floods and hazards. Texas Legislature could build on this foundation by amending Texas Property Code Section 92.0135 to strengthen and expand these protections in several key areas. First, the Legislature could extend the flooding history disclosure period from five years to ten years or the landlord's entire period of ownership, whichever is longer, to capture properties with recurring flood patterns that may fall outside a single five-year window. Second, the Legislature could expand geographic coverage to include properties identified as Severe Repetitive Loss or Repetitive Loss properties under the National Flood Insurance Program, which identify properties that have experienced multiple flood insurance claims and represent the highest-risk housing stock in disaster-prone communities. Specific to Texas too, because some Texans face risks beyond flooding, the Legislature could require landlords to disclose whether a property is located in a high or very high wildfire risk area as designated by the Texas A&M Forest Service Wildfire Risk Assessment, and whether the property is located in a county or region with elevated tornado frequency based on historical data maintained by the National Weather Service or the Texas Division of Emergency Management.

The Texas Legislature could also direct the Texas Department of Housing and Community Affairs, in consultation with the Texas Division of Emergency Management and the Texas Department of Insurance, to develop and publish a standardized multi-hazard disclosure form that landlords may use to satisfy disclosure requirements under Section 92.0135, addressing the current requirement that landlords provide notice in language "substantially equivalent" to statutory text, which creates variability and may reduce comprehension for tenants with limited English proficiency or unfamiliarity with flood and hazard terminology. The standardized form could be available in English, Spanish, Vietnamese, Chinese, and other languages commonly spoken in Texas. It could include plain-language explanations of flood zones, wildfire risk levels, tornado frequency, and the limitations of typical renter's insurance policies regarding flood and wind coverage. Legislators may also intentionally bracket language accessibility to areas and municipalities where English does not represent the majority of languages in a given census tract.

EXTENDING AND CLARIFYING LIMITING LIABILITY FOR GOOD SAMARITAN LICENSED ARCHITECTS AND PROFESSIONAL ENGINEERS FOR VOLUNTEER POST-DISASTER ASSESSMENT

Engineers and architects who act as Good Samaritans are important in disaster recovery. During the 80th Legislative Session, the Texas Legislature passed HB 823, which added Section 150.003 to the Civil Practice and Remedies Code providing that licensed architects and professional engineers who voluntarily provide services during a declared state of disaster under Section 418.014 of the Government Code, at the request or with the approval of a federal, state, or local public official, are immune from civil liability for any act, error, or omission unless it constitutes gross negligence or wanton, willful, or intentional misconduct. The Legislature subsequently extended similar protections to certified municipal inspectors through HB 403 during the 83rd Legislative Session, codified as Section 150.004.

These provisions have enabled rapid deployment of professional volunteers for building safety assessments following disasters such as Hurricane Harvey, Winter Storm Uri, and Hurricane Beryl. However, current law limits immunity to services provided "during the duration" of the declared disaster or emergency, creating undue uncertainty for volunteer professionals, as disaster declarations may be terminated or lapse. At the same time, recovery and rebuilding efforts continue for months or years thereafter. The Texas Legislature could amend Sections 150.003 and 150.004 of the Civil Practice and Remedies Code to extend civil liability immunity for volunteer architects, engineers, and certified municipal inspectors to a period of 90 days (again, can be negotiated) following the expiration or termination of a declared state of disaster or proclaimed state of emergency, or 180 days following the initial declaration, whichever is later. Extending the immunity period in Texas would provide clarity for volunteer professionals, reduce liability concerns that may deter participation in extended recovery efforts, and ensure that communities have access to qualified building safety assessments throughout the critical post-disaster rebuilding period. The anticipated fiscal note is minimal, but will have to be determined officially by the Texas Legislative Budget Board.

FACILITATING STATE-WIDE PRE-APPROVED DEBRIS MANAGEMENT SITES FOR CERTAIN COUNTIES PRONE TO DISASTER HAZARDS

The Texas Legislature could amend Chapter 418 of the Government Code or Chapter 361 of the Health and Safety Code to establish a tiered pre-authorization system for disaster debris management sites based on county disaster history and risk exposure. Following major disasters such as Hurricane Harvey, Hurricane Beryl, and Winter Storm Uri, Texas communities have faced significant delays in debris removal due to the need to identify, secure, and obtain TCEQ approval for temporary debris management sites. During Hurricane Harvey, TCEQ approved more than 100 Temporary Debris Management Sites statewide, which accelerated debris removal but were approved reactively, contributing to delays and occasional concerns about ad hoc sites. Still, the reactive approval process contributed to delays in debris removal and, in some cases, led to the establishment of unauthorized dump sites that raised environmental and public health concerns.

Under this proposal, Tier 1 counties (defined as counties located wholly or partially within a FEMA-designated coastal high-hazard area or hurricane evacuation zone, counties included in three or more federal or state disaster declarations within the preceding ten years, counties with a population exceeding 250,000, or counties designated by the Texas Division of Emergency Management as having high vulnerability based on the State Hazard Mitigation Plan) would be required to identify and obtain TCEQ pre-authorization for at least one disaster debris management site with annual renewal. Tier 2 counties (defined as counties included in one or two federal or state disaster declarations within the preceding ten years or adjacent to Tier 1 counties) would be encouraged but not required to obtain pre-authorization. They could receive priority consideration for Hazard Mitigation Grant Program funding and other state disaster preparedness grants if they voluntarily participate. All other counties would be permitted to obtain pre-authorization through a streamlined TCEQ process on a voluntary basis. Counties in any tier may satisfy pre-authorization requirements through mutual aid agreements or memoranda of understanding with adjacent counties to share pre-authorized sites, and regional councils of government could be authorized to coordinate multi-county debris management planning and obtain pre-authorization for regional sites serving multiple member counties.

EXPANDING LIABILITY PROTECTION OF WELFARE WORKERS WHO PROVIDE VOLUNTEER HEALTH CARE SERVICES TO CHARITABLE ORGANIZATIONS

Licensed Counselors, Respiratory Care Practitioners, Emergency Medical Technicians, Paramedics, and Radiologic Technologists all play a critical role in disaster recovery. The Texas Legislature could amend Section 84.003 of the Civil Practice and Remedies Code to expand the definition of "volunteer health care provider" to include licensed professional counselors under Chapter 503 of the Occupations Code, respiratory care practitioners under Chapter 604 of the Occupations Code, community health workers certified under Chapter 48 of the Health and Safety Code, emergency medical technicians and paramedics certified under Chapter 773 of the Health and Safety Code, and medical radiologic technologists licensed under Chapter 601 of the Occupations Code. The Charitable Immunity and Liability Act of 1987 provides that a volunteer health care provider serving as a direct service volunteer for a charitable organization is immune from civil liability for any act or omission that results in injury to a patient under certain circumstances. The statute defines "volunteer health care provider" to include physicians, nurses, dentists, social workers, and other licensed health professionals.

However, several categories of licensed and certified professionals who routinely provide critical services during disasters and through charitable health organizations remain excluded from these protections. Licensed professional counselors who provide psychotherapy and mental health treatment are not covered, despite their significant role in disaster response and community mental health. Respiratory care practitioners, who proved indispensable during the COVID-19 pandemic, lack equivalent immunity. Community health workers and promotoras, who serve as essential bridges between health care systems and underserved populations—particularly in diverse immigrant communities—are similarly unprotected. Emergency medical technicians and paramedics, who volunteer extensively at charitable events and disaster response operations, face liability exposure that may deter participation. Medical radiologic technologists, who provide diagnostic imaging services at free clinics and health fairs, are also excluded. Extending these protections would remove barriers to volunteerism, increase the availability of qualified health care professionals at charitable organizations and disaster response operations, and ensure that Texas communities have access to comprehensive volunteer health services. The anticipated fiscal note is minimal, but will have to be determined officially by the Texas Legislative Budget Board.

GENERATION AND POWER SUPPLY AT NURSING HOMES FOR VULNERABLE TEXANS

The Texas Legislature could amend Chapters 242 and 247 of the Health and Safety Code to require all nursing facilities and assisted living facilities to maintain operational emergency generators or comparable power sources with sufficient fuel to operate for at least 72 hours during power outages. Winter Storm Uri in 2021 and Hurricane Beryl in 2024 exposed critical vulnerabilities in Texas's care facility infrastructure, resulting in widespread power outages that placed elderly and medically fragile residents at severe risk.

Nursing home and assisted living residents are particularly vulnerable during extended outages due to temperature sensitivity, reliance on powered medical equipment, and limited mobility for evacuation. Current Texas law does not mandate backup power systems for these facilities, leaving compliance voluntary and inconsistent across the state. An excellent starting text encompassed in HB 1199 (89th Session) would require facilities to power areas of sufficient size to safely accommodate all residents, with additional, separately powered areas for facilities that utilize locking devices to restrict resident movement.

The bill permits flexibility in fuel sources, including natural gas, and establishes a compliance deadline with provisions allowing facilities to request extensions of up to 2 additional years in good faith. The Health and Human Services Commission would conduct annual inspections of emergency generators using a standardized checklist prescribed by rule. Enacting these requirements would protect Texas's most vulnerable residents during grid emergencies and ensure that care facilities are prepared for the increasing frequency of severe weather events. Harris County and Precinct 4 have also advanced substantial partnerships with the County's Fire Marshall, where Commissioner Lesley Briones, in partnership with Fire Marshal Laurie Christensen, unveiled a update to the Harris County Fire Code, aimed at safeguarding the county's most vulnerable residents. The new regulation requires assisted living and nursing facilities in unincorporated Harris County to install backup power systems that will ensure critical heating and cooling systems remain operational during emergencies. .

CITY OF HOUSTON CIP FUNDING ALLOCATION

The City of Houston could allocate Capital Improvement Project (Known as CIP) and Council District Service Funds (CDSF) specifically for green-blue dual-use infrastructure in District F and the Alief community, including parks designed with stormwater retention capacity, trail systems incorporating bioswales and detention features, and recreational facilities that serve as emergency flood storage during storm events. The Brays Bayou watershed, which flows eastward through Alief parallel to the Westpark Tollway, encompasses approximately 128 square miles with more than 1,000 miles of storm sewer within city limits and contains over 34,000 structures in the 100-year floodplain. Keegans Bayou, which feeds into Brays Bayou through South Alief, has repeatedly overtopped its banks during significant rain events, including Tropical Storm Beta in 2020, when nearly 100 high-water rescues were conducted citywide, and areas near NRG Park received as much as 12 inches of rain in 24 hours.

District F presents multiple opportunities for dual-use investments along these bayou corridors, including Hackberry Park and Boone Park, which are already in the queue. The Old Alief Regional David Hennington Library site offers additional opportunities to integrate stormwater management features into a civic anchor that serves the diverse Alief community. These investments would follow the successful model of Arthur Storey Park along Brays Bayou, which functions as both a public recreational space and a detention basin capable of holding approximately 1.1 billion gallons of water during flood events. Prioritizing dual-use infrastructure in Alief would maximize the value of limited capital funds while addressing equity gaps in park access and flood protection for one of Harris County's most culturally diverse and historically underserved communities.

ALTERNATE OWNERSHIP DOCUMENTATION FOR CDBG-DR APPLICANTS

The City of Houston Governmental Affairs Team could work with HUD to accept alternate forms of ownership documentation for homeowners applying for Community Development Block Grant-Disaster Recovery funds, while developing standardized affidavits of ownership for heirs' property owners and others without clear title documentation. Heirs' property is family land inherited without a will or traditional documentation. It represents one of the most unstable forms of property ownership and is disproportionately found in Black, Latino, low-income, and low-wealth families in both rural and urban communities. More than a third of Black-owned land in the South is heir's property, a practice dating to Reconstruction when many Black families lacked access to courts and continuing through the Jim Crow era. A ProPublica-New Yorker investigation revealed how heir property owners are routinely locked out of federal assistance and can be compelled by courts to sell their land against their will through forced partition sales.

Following the investigation, U.S. Representative Lizzie Fletcher of Texas introduced the HEIR Act of 2024, alongside Representatives Nikema Williams of Georgia and Emanuel Cleaver of Missouri, which would amend HUD regulations to allow heir property owners to use alternative documentation to qualify for disaster aid. The legislation echoes a policy adopted by FEMA in 2021, after a Washington Post analysis revealed a pattern of denying assistance to heir property owners. In 2022, FEMA distributed \$350 million in disaster assistance to heirs' property owners and extended relief to 42,000 homeowners who had previously been denied aid.

However, HUD has not made similar changes to CDBG-DR requirements, leaving long-term recovery assistance inaccessible to many disaster survivors. A companion bill, the HEIRS Act of 2024, would authorize \$300 million over ten years for HUD to reward states that adopt the Uniform Partition of Heirs Property Act and create a \$10 million annual program to fund nonprofits providing legal assistance to heirs property owners who cannot afford to clear titles. As Representative Fletcher noted, the data reveal staggering amounts of lost generational wealth because of how the system operates. Houston could advocate for HUD to implement these changes administratively while federal legislation works through Congress. The City of Houston and related non-profit entities should formalize assistance to those who need it for title issues and inheritance cases.

COMMUNITY-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS

In addition to the prior policy recommendations, AliefVotes, on Saturday, December 6, 2025, hosted a Texas Legislative policy workshop to refine and further develop the recommendations in this report. AliefVotes also led an extensive revision process in which community stakeholders could provide detailed, page-by-page feedback online and in person. Through sticky notes, roundtable conversation notes, and a comprehensive feedback form, the following issues have been identified by the community as integral to consider in disaster preparedness planning in the neighborhood.

Alief Disaster Preparedness Protocol

Thank you so much for your support and collaboration throughout this project. As we continue improving the Alief Disaster Preparedness Protocol, **your feedback is incredibly important to us.** We want to ensure that this report reflects the needs, experiences, and perspectives of our community as accurately and meaningfully as possible. **We would like to credit all editors who fill out this form, if you so choose.**

To help us strengthen the next iteration, please take a few minutes to fill out the feedback form below. Your insights—whether on clarity, accuracy, structure, or additional recommendations—will directly guide our revisions.

Figure 56. Texas Legislative Policy Workshop on Saturday, December 6, 2025 at the Chinese Community Center. On the right was the Alief Disaster Preparedness Protocol Feedback Form, leading to 28 detailed responses from non-profit, government, and community stakeholders. Edits were conducted by students for the final report.

Figure 57. To ensure multiple opportunities for comprehensive feedback, AliefVotes students designed sticky note activities, on top of community roundtables and online feedback portals.

COMMUNITY-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS

Kyle Frese, Founder of Decentralized Farming LLC & Alief Resident

- Building on existing pocket prairie initiatives, Alief could expand green infrastructure investments across residential, commercial, governmental, and faith-based properties through the installation of swales, rain gardens, and rainwater capture systems by leveraging the community's 100,000+ residents to reduce stormwater runoff and flood risk significantly.
- Concurrent shade tree planting efforts could continue alongside educational programming on food seasonality, which can improve community resilience during extreme heat events and power outages by promoting consumption of locally grown, seasonal produce. Notably, with approximately 4,500 acres of green space across Alief's 14 square miles and demonstrated local capacity to produce 90% of household food needs on just one-eighth of an acre, the community holds theoretical potential to feed roughly 36,000 residents through distributed urban agriculture, representing a compelling case for integrating food security into broader disaster preparedness and climate adaptation strategies.

The Plant Based Treaty

- Disaster relief plans and emergency food distributions could include and, when feasible, prioritize plant-based options such as shelf-stable staples (dried or low-sodium canned beans, lentils, chickpeas, vegetables, fruits, rice, oats, pasta) and ready-to-eat plant-based meals (soups, stews, curries, chili, shelf-stable tofu, plant-based proteins). These items could be either the default or easy to request, clearly labeled, and treated as a normal part of the food supply so people with different cultural, religious, and health needs have more choices in an emergency, not fewer.
- The City could provide public information and education about healthy, plant-based foods as a practical way to build healthier communities, especially in underserved areas, highlighting how plant-rich eating supports optimal health and can help prevent or manage chronic illnesses such as cancer, heart disease, diabetes, and obesity. Resources could be available across city and partner platforms using clear, accessible language and trusted messengers.

COMMUNITY-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS

The Plant Based Treaty, Continued

- A youth-led food security and sustainability advisory board could be created to support plant-forward cooking, nutrition, and disaster-preparedness activities through existing after-school programs, fellowships, and community events, working alongside partners, community leaders, school representatives, and nutrition service staff to co-design plant-rich menus and ensure changes feel community-driven.
- Voluntary tax credits or financial incentives could be created for institutions and vendors that choose to expand plant-based options, including modest local tax credits for food service providers offering plant-based main dishes, small grants or low-interest financing for retailers in high-need areas, and priority access to existing incentive programs for businesses sourcing plant-based products.

Naomi Ostfield, Brays Oaks Super Neighborhood Council #36

- “Just as [AliefVotes] included milkweeds for the Monarch butterflies, I'd like future Pocket Prairies to include plants that are food and provide safe rest spots for birds who fly over the Houston area during their migrations south and then back north each year.”

Francisco Garcia, Houston Health Department & Alief Leader

- Despite a proven ROI (\$6 saved for every \$1 invested), federal PDM programs like FEMA's BRIC are underfunded. Alief's aging infrastructure regularly fails, causing millions in damages. We advocate for a dedicated 10% set-aside from all disaster appropriations for direct PDM grants to vulnerable communities, bypassing competitive state processes. This empowers local governments to proactively invest in upgrades (e.g., covered drainage, cooling centers), estimated at \$2-3 billion annually nationwide, significantly reducing future disaster costs and saving lives.
- Federal funding often triggers lengthy NEPA environmental reviews, delaying disaster recovery projects by months or years. For example, repairs to Alief community centers post-Harvey were significantly delayed. We recommend a tiered review system: expedited review for routine repairs and pre-approved mitigation in disaster zones, with full review for new construction or significant impacts. Lessons from expedited permitting for renewable energy could inform this, ensuring environmental protection without crippling recovery.

COMMUNITY-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS

Francisco Garcia, Houston Health Department & Alief Leader, Continued

- **Emergency Rental Assistance:** This policy establishes a permanent, continuously funded city program to provide immediate financial relief and housing support for tenants displaced by declared disasters. The program would offer direct rental assistance, temporary housing vouchers, and relocation support for up to 12 months. This is crucial as many low-income Houstonians, particularly renters, lack savings for unexpected displacement, and federal aid often arrives slowly or with strict eligibility requirements. After Harvey, thousands of Alief residents found themselves homeless or in precarious living situations, unable to afford security deposits or first month's rent for new apartments while their old ones were uninhabitable. This program would bridge that gap, preventing homelessness and facilitating rapid recovery.
- **Mandatory Apartment Plans:** This policy mandates that all multi-family residential complexes with 50 or more units submit and regularly update comprehensive Emergency Preparedness Plans to the Houston Fire Department (HFD). These plans must detail evacuation procedures, shelter-in-place protocols, communication strategies for residents (including multilingual options), emergency power sources, and methods for assisting residents with special needs. Complexes would be required to conduct annual disaster drills and provide residents with simplified, multilingual guides to the plan. Many Alief apartment complexes during previous disasters were ill-prepared, leaving residents confused about evacuation routes, struggling with power outages, and lacking clear instructions, especially non-English speakers. This ensures that landlords take proactive steps to protect their tenants and that residents are better informed and prepared.

IDENTIFIED COMMUNITY CONCERNS IN ALIEF

- One resident described getting stuck on the highway while evacuating due to flooding. The evacuation routes proved insufficient and created hazardous conditions, particularly on the roads. During this experience, they ran out of water and power while stranded. This highlights the critical need for improved evacuation route planning, with a specific emphasis on highway infrastructure and capacity during flood events.
- A student was in 4th grade at Martin Elementary School during the 2019 flood. The floodwaters rose during school hours while students were inside the building. The situation became so dangerous that students had to jump out of the school through the windows. This experience demonstrates the acute vulnerability of schools during flood events and the need for robust school emergency protocols that account for rapid water rise scenarios.
- A caregiver of elderly people raised significant concerns about the impact of power loss on those in their care. They emphasized that power outages in Alief don't require a considerable flood—they occur frequently and create immediate challenges for elderly care, including the operation of medical equipment, temperature regulation, and medication storage. The participant also raised questions about the use of community centers during emergencies and asked a critical question: Do the people in Alief know that these resources are accessible to them during disasters?
- Ayo emphasized that Alief is a highly diverse community with many residents who don't speak English as a first language. These communities often aren't informed about the issues and dangers, and why that information matters for their safety. The recommendation was to prominently highlight language access in the final report, recognizing it as a fundamental equity issue in disaster preparedness.

Figure 58. A group shot of the community at the December 6, 2026 disaster preparedness policy roundtable and feedback session, in which residents provided invaluable feedback to the first draft of our report.

IDENTIFIED COMMUNITY CONCERNS IN ALIEF

- Dr. Joy Semien, who teaches disaster preparedness, stressed that language translation alone is insufficient for effective emergency communication. Disaster response must be culturally appropriate and account for the community's diverse religions and cultural practices. She noted that Spanish may not be suitable for specific communities in Alief, given the diversity of Asian, African, and other populations present. The focus needs to be on social and cultural differences, not just linguistic translation. Cultural competency must accompany all language access efforts to be truly effective.
- A participant asked whether a foreigner would have enough resources during a disaster. Given Alief's diverse community, people who don't share a common language must still survive disasters together. One of the key challenges identified is communicating with people who don't speak the same language while trying to survive a disaster together. This represents a fundamental resilience issue, not merely a convenience concern.
- Dr. Joy Semien, former Chief of Staff for the EPA, warned that we are currently in an era of government policy changes where the government may or may not continue helping communities at current levels. She noted that the City has inherent limitations on what it can directly provide. Immigrant populations want the same access to resources as other residents, and the focus should be on bringing resources directly to the community rather than expecting community members to navigate complex systems to access help.
- Kyle Frese observed that the County and City are doing significant preparation work. He follows District F and Councilwoman Thomas on social media and has noted that they consistently share information about warming centers and other emergency resources. There is recognition that substantial preparation work is happening at the local government level in response to community needs.

Additional Recommendations

- Participants recommended advising officials and emergency responders to be aware of the needs of the low vision and deaf communities during disaster response. Creating picture guides would allow people to point to their situation during emergencies when verbal communication isn't possible. Non-verbal communication tools are essential for emergencies involving disabled residents.
- A tool exists on the City of Houston website as part of their data portal, established in 1997, that allows residents to check if contractors are fraudulent. Transparency in the market is a valuable prerogative of local government. While better technology exists, it remains hard to implement. Importantly, having resources in multiple languages also means ensuring they are easy to use.

EXPANSION & REPLICATION

This protocol is transformational because it encapsulates the work led by youth over the past three years that directly addressed residents' concerns about disaster preparedness and recovery. Our efforts, though, must not stop here. Trust can be built, but it must be continued through practical efforts, not just in Alief, but in as many communities as possible in the greater Houston area. Whether it's Acres Home, Fifth Ward, Galena Park, or any other community, we all face unique challenges. Imagine the fundamental shift our city could have if each community had dedicated organizers, community engagement opportunities, and effort-driven partners that truly listen to community members and their concerns.

Alief is all about action. And there is always more we can do.

Figure 59. Alief is all about action. The photos above showcases the innate nature of our youth and generational partners.

FINAL THOUGHTS & CALL TO ACTION

Alief—our power is not above us, nor beneath us. It’s in us. This goes for disaster preparedness, community resilience, and the idea that we can do even more when we do it together. Thank you to all partners, funders, and, most importantly, the student leaders who have led this multi-year effort to ensure that our communities are cared for. Readers, I urge you to share this report, talk about it in multiple languages at the dining table, present these policy recommendations to your local officials, and realize that once disaster strikes, we do have the innate ability to come together and serve. That’s what community is all about.

Figure 60. AliefVotes events over the past year, showcasing an unwavering love of our microcosm of a community in Houston.

With the most sincere appreciation, love, and passion for S.W.A.T. (Southwest, Alief, Texas), we hereby sign off to not just a static report, but a dynamic effort that will continue for years to come.

Tommy Wan, Lead Author

Julian Nguyen, Co-Lead Editor

Lander Gonzalez

Ericka Chanchavac-Rosales

Cindy Ukwu

Harrison Tran, Co-Lead Editor

Zody Calderon-Huerta

Sawsan Busari

Allie Hogan

Yousif Al Mashhadi

RESOURCE DIRECTORY

Emergency Numbers

- Emergency: 911
- City of Houston Services: 3-1-1
- Texas Information & Referral: 2-1-1
- Harris Center Mental Health Crisis: 713-970-7000
- Suicide & Crisis Lifeline: 988

Alert Systems

- AlertHouston: houstonemergency.org/alerts
- ReadyHarris: Text R-E-A-D-Y to 281-609-9093
- STEAR Registry (special needs): <https://stear.texas.gov/>

Food Assistance

- Houston Food Bank: 713-223-3700, houstonfoodbank.org
- SNAP/Food Stamps: YourTexasBenefits.com
- Texas Department of Health and Human Services (for SNAP)
 - 2-1-1 or 877-541-7905

Housing & Financial Assistance

- FEMA: DisasterAssistance.gov, 800-621-3362 and egateway.fema.gov/ESF6/DRCLocator
- City of Houston Housing: 832-394-6200 and hcd@houstontx.gov
- BakerRipley: 713-667-9400
- Catholic Charities: 713-526-4611

Healthcare (Multilingual)

- HOPE Clinic: 713-773-0803 (30+ languages)
- Legacy Community Health: 832-548-5000
- Harris Health (Gold Card): 713-566-6509
- Bellaire Dialysis: 14412 Bellaire Blvd, Houston, TX 77083, 281-575-8000

Immigrant Services

- YMCA International Services: 713-758-9280
- Catholic Charities Immigration: 713-526-4611
- BakerRipley Immigration Legal: 713-667-9400
- IM Houston Refugee Services: 713-533-4900
- HCPH Refugee Clinic: 713-274-2599

Mental Health

- The Harris Center: 713-970-7000
- 988 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline: 988

Precinct 4 Service Lines:

- Email: service@hcp4.net or Phone 832-927-4444
- Texas General Land Office of Texas (GLO) allocates funding for disaster recovery efforts to repair and rebuild.
 - Recovery hotline: 1-844-893-8937 (Toll Free) or email: CDR@Recovery.Texas.Gov
- Disaster Field Operations Center at 916-735-1500

For more disaster resources, visit: <https://tinyurl.com/alief-more-resources>

ITEMS FOR DISASTER KIT

Water & Hydration

- 1 gallon of water per person per day for drinking and sanitation (minimum 3 gallons per person, ideally 7 gallons).
- A full bathtub (if you have one) before disaster strikes.
- Electrolyte packets during extended heat waves.

Food & Cooking

- Non-perishable stock requiring no cooking that includes goods like canned items, peanut butter, crackers, and ready-to-eat meals.
- Butane burner for cooking, if needed in more extended outages.
- Manual can opener.
- Infant formula for newborns, mess kits, and paper disposable utensils.
- Snacks.

Power & Communication

- Flashlights and extra batteries (at least two flashlights, and ensure that your family knows of their placement).
- A battery-powered or hand-crank radio for emergency broadcasts.
- Cell phone chargers, like portable battery packs and car chargers.
- Mobile and laptop chargers in various locations.
- Whistle to signal for help.

First Aid & Medical

- First aid kit with bandages, antiseptics, and pain relievers.
- 7-day supply of all prescriptions plus copies of prescriptions (brief those that you take care of, especially).

Important Documents & Money

- Cash: \$200-500 in small bills (ATMs and card readers can fail during outages).
- Important documents in a waterproof container that include, at a minimum, your IDs, insurance policies, medical records, immigration documents, property deeds, and vehicle titles.

Hygiene & Sanitation

- Toilet paper, hand sanitizer, soap, feminine products, and diapers.
- Moist towels, garbage bags, and disinfectants for sanitation.
- Toothpaste, toothbrushes, and wet wipes.

ITEMS FOR DISASTER KIT, CONT.

Tools & Safety Equipment

- Fire extinguishers and waterproofed matches.
- Dust masks and plastic sheeting for sheltering in place (optional).
- Wrench or pliers to turn off utilities.
- Knowledge of how to shut off your water main.

Home Protection & Repairs

- Plastic tarps for any emergency roof repairs.
- Plywood or hurricane shutters, tarps, duct tape, rope for fast repairs.
- Pipe insulation tape.

Planning & Navigation

- Local maps, if you have them.
- An easy-to-understand meeting place for your family.

Pet Preparedness

- Food, water, medications, carrier, vaccination records, and ID tags for your pets.

Cultural & Community Considerations

- Store non-perishable versions of culturally appropriate foods (halal, kosher, vegetarian options available at Hong Kong Market, 99 Ranch, H-Mart on Bellaire, Fiesta).
- Stock of prayer items, religious texts, or spiritual comfort items.
- Copies of immigration documents, visas, green cards, and work permits with your emergency documents in a waterproof bag.
- Emergency contact information written in your native language and especially provided to family members who do not speak English. You may even elect to do an audio version for them.

Special Medical Needs & Disabilities

- Apply for Centerpoint's Chronic Condition or Critical Care Residential Customer Status at 713-207-2222.
- Register with STEAR (State of Texas Emergency Assistance Registry): 211texas.org/stear or call 2-1-1.
- Have backup batteries or a generator plan for life-sustaining equipment.
- Keep a written list of all medical equipment, medications, and dosages.
- Know the location of the nearest hospital and dialysis center.
- Have a manual wheelchair if you use a powered one.
- Store extra supplies: catheters, oxygen, feeding supplies, etc.

"When disaster strikes, the time to prepare has passed." - Steven Cyros

CREDITS & FUNDERS

Funded by the Resilient Cities Network. Lead Author: Tommy Wan. Student Editors & Writers: Julian Nguyen, Harrison Tran, Lander Gonzalez, Zody Calderon-Huerta, Allie Hogan, Ericka Chanchavac-Rosales, Sawsan Busari, Cindy Ukwu, and Yousif Al Mashhadi.

HARRIS COUNTY PRECINCT 4
COMMISSIONER
LESLEY BRIONES

With support from Texas State Representative Gene Wu's Office & Consulate General of Mexico in Houston.